

The inter-universal Teichmüller theory and new Diophantine results over the rational numbers. I

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Abstract

By applying inter-universal Teichmüller theory and its slight modification over the rational number field, we prove new Diophantine results towards effective abc inequalities and the generalized Fermat equations.

For coprime integers a, b, c satisfying $a + b = c$ and $\log(|abc|) \geq 700$, we prove

$$\log |abc| \leq 3 \log \text{rad}(abc) + 8 \sqrt{\log |abc| \cdot \log \log |abc|}.$$

This implies for any $0 < \epsilon \leq \frac{1}{10}$,

$$|abc| \leq \max \left\{ \exp(400 \cdot \epsilon^{-2} \cdot \log(\epsilon^{-1})), \text{rad}(abc)^{3+3\epsilon} \right\},$$

reducing the constant in effective abc bounds from $1.7 \cdot 10^{30}$ (Mochizuki-Fesenko-Hoshi-Minamide-Porowski) to 400.

For positive primitive solutions (x, y, z) to the generalized Fermat equation $x^r + y^s = z^t$ ($r, s, t \geq 3$), define $h = \log(x^r y^s z^t)$. We prove explicit bounds:

$$\begin{aligned} h &\leq 573 \quad (r, s, t \geq 8); \quad h \leq 907 \quad (r, s, t \geq 5); \quad h \leq 2283 \quad (r, s, t \geq 4); \\ h &\leq 14750 \quad (\min\{r, s\} \geq 4 \text{ or } t \geq 4); \quad h \leq 24626 \quad (r, s, t \geq 3). \end{aligned}$$

These imply Fermat's Last Theorem (FLT) holds unconditionally for prime exponents ≥ 11 . Combined with classical results for FLT with exponents 3, 4, 5, 7, this yields a new alternative proof of FLT. Computational verification confirms no non-trivial primitive solution exists when $r, s, t \geq 20$ or (r, s, t) is a permutation of $(3, 3, n)$ ($n \geq 3$).

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Introduction

In the recent paper [39], Shinichi Mochizuki, Ivan B. Fesenko, Yuichiro Hoshi, Arata Minamide, and Wojciech Porowski established a μ_6 -version of Mochizuki’s inter-universal Teichmüller theory (IUT theory) [cf. [35–38]], proving the following Diophantine results [cf. [39], Theorem B and Corollary C]:

Theorem. *Let a, b, c be non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b + c = 0$, and let ϵ be a positive real number ≤ 1 . Then we have*

$$|abc| \leq 2^4 \cdot \max \left\{ \exp \left(1.7 \cdot 10^{30} \cdot \epsilon^{-166/81} \right), \text{rad}(abc)^{3+3\epsilon} \right\}.$$

Corollary. *Let*

$$p > 1.615 \cdot 10^{14}$$

be a prime number. Then there does not exist any triple (x, y, z) of positive integers that satisfies the Fermat equation

$$x^p + y^p = z^p.$$

In the present paper, we slightly modify some of the methods in [38, 39] for the special case of rational numbers, to estimate the log-volumes of $[\mu_6]$ -initial Θ -data more precisely. Then, by focusing on the Frey-Hellegouarch curves, we prove new effective versions of abc inequalities for rational numbers:

Theorem A1. *Let (a, b, c) be a triple of non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b = c$.*

(i) Suppose that $\log(|abc|) \geq 700$, then we have

$$\log(|abc|) \leq 3 \log \text{rad}(abc) + 8 \sqrt{\log(|abc|) \cdot \log \log(|abc|)}.$$

(ii) Suppose that $\log(|abc|) \geq 3 \cdot 10^{13}$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \log(|abc|) \leq & 3 \log \text{rad}(abc) + 3 \sqrt{\log(|abc|) \cdot \log \log(|abc|)} \\ & \cdot \left(1 + \frac{6}{\sqrt{\log \log(|abc|)}} + \frac{15}{\log \log(|abc|)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary A2. *Let (a, b, c) be a triple of non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b = c$; ϵ be a positive real number $\leq \frac{1}{10}$. Then we have*

$$|abc| \leq \max \left\{ \exp \left(400 \cdot \epsilon^{-2} \cdot \log(\epsilon^{-1}) \right), \text{rad}(abc)^{3+3\epsilon} \right\}.$$

We also conduct a preliminary study on the generalized Fermat equations. Let $r, s, t \geq 2$ be positive integers. The equation

$$x^r + y^s = z^t, \text{ with } x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z}$$

is known as the generalized Fermat equation with signature (r, s, t) . A solution (x, y, z) is called non-trivial if $xyz \neq 0$, primitive if $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$, and positive if $x, y, z \geq 1$.

Theorem B1. *Let $r, s, t \geq 3$ be positive integers. Write*

$$S(r, s, t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}^3 : x^r + y^s = z^t, \gcd(x, y, z) = 1\}$$

for the finite set of positive primitive solutions to the generalized Fermat equation with signature (r, s, t) . Define

$$f(r, s, t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sup_{(x, y, z) \in S} \log(x^r y^s z^t) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0},$$

where we shall write $f(r, s, t) = 0$ if $S(r, s, t)$ is an empty set.

Then we have $f(r, s, t) \leq 573$ for $r, s, t \geq 8$; $f(r, s, t) \leq 907$ for $r, s, t \geq 5$; $f(r, s, t) \leq 2283$ for $r, s, t \geq 4$; $f(r, s, t) \leq 14750$ for $\min\{r, s\} \geq 4$ or $t \geq 4$; and $f(r, s, t) \leq 24626$ for $r, s, t \geq 3$.

Corollary B2. *Let*

$$p \geq 11$$

be a prime number. Then there does not exist any triple (x, y, z) of positive integers that satisfies the Fermat equation

$$x^p + y^p = z^p.$$

Corollary B2, combined with the classical results about the non-existence of positive integer solutions (x, y, z) of the Fermat equation

$$x^n + y^n = z^n$$

for $n = 3$ (Euler), $n = 4$ (Fermat), $n = 5$ (Dirichlet and Legendre) and $n = 7$ (Gabriel Lamé), yields an **unconditional new alternative proof** [i.e., to the proof of [49] and a certain simplification of its second proof in [39]] of **Fermat's Last Theorem**.

Corollary B3. *Let r, s, t be positive integers such that $r, s, t \geq 20$, or (r, s, t) is a permutation of $(3, 3, n)$ for $n \geq 3$. Then there does not exist any triple (x, y, z) of non-zero coprime integers that satisfies the generalized Fermat equation*

$$x^r + y^s = z^t.$$

In the subsequent paper, we will introduce new insights to further explore the generalized Fermat equations. Specifically, we will establish new upper bounds for non-trivial primitive solutions and demonstrate the non-existence of such solutions for an expanded set of signatures.

The present paper is organized as follows. In Section 1, we provide an estimate for the log-volume of μ_6 -initial Θ -data [cf. Proposition 1.10], which is a slightly modified version of [38], Theorem 1.10, and [39], Theorem 5.1. The μ_6 -version of [37], Corollary 3.12, proven in [39], plays a key role in this Section. Its proof relies on strong anabelian geometry results primarily established by Mochizuki.

In Section 2, for any triple of non-zero coprime integers (a, b, c) such that $a + b = c$, we first construct the μ_6 -initial Θ -data associated with the Frey-Hellegouarch curve $y^2 = x(x - a)(x + b)$. By applying the estimation from Section 1 to these μ_6 -initial Θ -data, we obtain "partial abc inequalities" associated with (a, b, c) .

Section 3 is devoted to proving several effective abc inequalities. Finally, in Section 4, we study upper bounds for positive primitive solutions to the generalized Fermat equations.

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0 Notations and Conventions

General Notations:

For a real number λ , we shall write $\lfloor \lambda \rfloor$ for the largest integer $n \leq \lambda$, and write $\lceil \lambda \rceil$ for the smallest integer $n \geq \lambda$. For a finite set I , we shall write $|I|$ for the the cardinality of I . For a finite field extension K/L , we shall write $[K : L]$ for the extension degree $\dim_L K$. For a field K or a ring R , we shall write K^\times or R^\times for the group of invertible elements in K or R .

Let n be a non-zero integer. The radical of n , denoted by $\text{rad}(n)$, is the product of the distinct prime factors of n . For any integer $k \geq 2$, the k -radical of n , denoted by $\text{rad}_k(n)$, is the product of the distinct prime factors p of n , where the p -adic valuation $v_p(n)$ of n is not divided by k . Hence we have

$$\text{rad}(n) = \prod_{p|n} p, \quad \text{rad}_k(n) = \prod_{k \nmid v_p(n)} p.$$

Let p be a prime number. We shall write \mathbb{Q} (respectively, \mathbb{R} ; \mathbb{C} ; \mathbb{Q}_p ; \mathbb{F}_p) for the field of rational numbers (respectively, real numbers; complex numbers; p -adic rational numbers; the finite field with p elements), and write \mathbb{Z} (respectively, \mathbb{Z}_p) for the ring of rational integers (respectively, the ring of p -adic integers).

We shall call finite extension of \mathbb{Q} number field, call finite extension of \mathbb{Q}_p p -adic local field, call \mathbb{R} real archimedean local field, and call \mathbb{C} complex archimedean local field.

We shall write \mathfrak{Primes} for the set of prime numbers. For each prime number $l \geq 3$, we shall put $l^* \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{l-1}{2}$.

Number Fields:

Let L be an arbitrary number field. We shall use $\mathbb{V}(L)$ to denote the set of valuations of L , and use $\mathbb{V}(L)^{\text{non}}$ (respectively, $\mathbb{V}(L)^{\text{arc}}$) to denote the set of nonarchimedean (respectively, archimedean) valuations of L . Here, all the valuations are assumed to be normalized.

For the case $L = \mathbb{Q}$, we shall put $\mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{V}(\mathbb{Q})$, and put $\mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\square} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{V}(\mathbb{Q})^{\square}$ for $\square \in \{\text{non}, \text{arc}\}$. Then we have $\mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}} = \{v_p : p \in \mathfrak{Primes}\}$ and $\mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{arc}} = \{v_{\mathbb{R}}\}$, where v_p is the p -adic valuation on \mathbb{Q} , and $v_{\mathbb{R}}$ is the unique archimedean valuation on \mathbb{Q} . For a prime number p and a rational number x , if $v_p(x) \geq 1$, then we shall say p divides x , and write it as $p \mid x$; if $v_p(x) \leq 0$, then we shall say p does not divide x , and write it as $p \nmid x$.

Let K/L be a finite extension of number fields. For each $v \in \mathbb{V}(L)$, we shall use $\mathbb{V}(K)_v$ to denote the [finite] set of valuations of K lying over v . Then we have

$$\sum_{v \in \mathbb{V}(K)_v} [K_v : L_v] = [K : L].$$

An $[\mathbb{R}]$ -arithmetic divisor on L is a finite formal sum $\mathbf{a} = \sum_{v \in \mathbb{V}(L)} c_v \cdot v$, where $c_v \in \mathbb{R}$. We shall use $\text{ADiv}_{\mathbb{R}}(L)$ to denote the abelian group of $[\mathbb{R}]$ -arithmetic divisors on L . The degree of \mathbf{a} is defined by the formula

$$\deg_L(\mathbf{a}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{v \in \mathbb{V}(L)^{\text{non}}} c_v \cdot \log(|\kappa(L_v)|) + \sum_{v \in \mathbb{V}(L)^{\text{arc}}} c_v,$$

where $\kappa(L_v)$ is the [finite] residue field of L_v . The normalized degree of \mathbf{a} is defined by the formula

$$\underline{\deg}(\mathbf{a}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{[L : \mathbb{Q}]} \deg_L(\mathbf{a}).$$

Thus for any finite extension K of L , we have $\underline{\deg}(\mathbf{a}|_K) = \underline{\deg}(\mathbf{a})$, where we write $\mathbf{a}|_K$ for the the pull-back [defined in the evident fashion] of \mathbf{a} to an arithmetic divisor on K .

Local Fields:

For an archimedean local field k [i.e. \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C}] with absolute value $|\cdot|_k$, we shall write

$$\mathcal{O}_k \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{x \in k, |x|_k \leq 1\}$$

for the unit ball of k .

Let p be a prime number, k be a p -adic local field. The p -adic valuation v_p on \mathbb{Q} extends naturally to \mathbb{Q}_p and k , and we shall write \mathcal{O}_k for the ring of integers of k . We shall call the p -adic valuation of any generator of the different ideal of \mathcal{O}_k over \mathbb{Z}_p as the **different index** of k .

Let e be the ramification index of k over \mathbb{Q}_p , $\pi_k \in k$ be a uniformizer of k , R_k be the group of multiplicative representatives in the unit group of \mathcal{O}_k . Then we have an group isomorphism

$$k^\times \cong \pi_k^{\mathbb{Z}} \times R_k \times (1 + \pi_k \mathcal{O}_k).$$

For each $x = \pi_k^a \cdot u \cdot (1 + t) \in k^\times$ according to the this group isomorphism, the p -adic logarithm function $\log_p : k^\times \rightarrow k$ is defined by the formula

$$\log_p(x) = \log_p(1 + t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{t^n}{n}.$$

For each $t \in k^\times$ with $v_p(t) > \frac{1}{p-1}$, the p -adic exponent function $\exp_p : \{t \in k : v_p(t) > \frac{1}{p-1}\} \rightarrow k^\times$ is defined by the formula

$$\exp_p(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^n}{n!}.$$

For each $t \in k$ with $v_p(t) > \frac{1}{p-1}$, we have $\log_p(\exp_p(t)) = t$.

Curves:

Let K be a field of characteristic zero with an algebraic closure \overline{K} , E be an elliptic curve defined over K , $n \geq 1$ be an positive integer. Then we shall write $E[n]$ for the group of n -torsion points of $E_{\overline{K}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \times_K \overline{K}$, and write $K(E[n]) \subseteq \overline{K}$ for the "n-torsion point field" of E , i.e. the field generated by K and the coordinates of the points in $E[n]$.

1 Modified Estimation for Log-volumes

This section is devoted to the estimation for log-volumes in IUT theory. We shall prove Proposition 1.10, which is a modified version of [38], Theorem 1.10 and [39], Theorem 5.1. The majority of the results in this section can be viewed as slight modifications of [38], Section 1 and [39], Theorem 5.1.

1.1 Estimation for Local Log-volumes

We shall begin with some estimation for local log-volumes.

Lemma 1.1. *Let $\{k_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a finite set of p -adic local fields [cf. §0], where $|I| \geq 2$. For each $i \in I$, write π_i for a uniformizer of k_i ; \mathcal{O}_{k_i} for the ring of integers of k_i ; e_i for the ramification index of k_i over \mathbb{Q}_p ; $d_i \in \frac{1}{e_i} \mathbb{Z}$ for the different index [cf. §0] of k_i .*

(i) *We shall write*

$$R_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigotimes_{i \in I} \mathcal{O}_{k_i}, \quad \log_p(R_I^\times) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigotimes_{i \in I} \log_p(\mathcal{O}_{k_i}^\times),$$

where the tensor product is over \mathbb{Z}_p ; write $(R_I)^\sim$ for the normalization of R_I in its ring of fractions R' . Then we have

$$R' = \mathbb{Q}_p \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_p} R_I = \mathbb{Q}_p \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_p} \log_p(R_I^\times) = \bigotimes_{i \in I} k_i,$$

where the last tensor product is over \mathbb{Q}_p . We also have direct sum decompositions

$$R' = \bigoplus_{i=1}^{n_{R'}} L_i \quad \text{and} \quad (R_I)^\sim = \bigoplus_{i=1}^{n_{R'}} \mathcal{O}_{L_i},$$

where for each $1 \leq i \leq n_{R'}$, L_i is a p -adic local field with ring of integers \mathcal{O}_{L_i} .

(ii) *For each*

$$\vec{\lambda} = (\lambda_i)_{i \in I} \in \Lambda_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigoplus_{i \in I} \frac{1}{e_i} \cdot \mathbb{Z},$$

we shall call

$$\deg(\vec{\lambda}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{i \in I} \lambda_i \in \Lambda \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{\gcd_{i \in I} \{e_i\}} \mathbb{Z}$$

the degree of $\vec{\lambda}$, and write

$$p^{\vec{\lambda}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigotimes_{i \in I} \pi_i^{\lambda_i e_i} \in R_I.$$

Then the set $p^{\vec{\lambda}} \cdot (R_I)^\sim$ is determined by $\deg(\vec{\lambda})$ [i.e. independent of the choice of π_i , λ_i for $i \in I$], and we shall write

$$p^{\deg(\vec{\lambda})} \cdot (R_I)^\sim \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} p^{\vec{\lambda}} \cdot (R_I)^\sim.$$

Moreover, for any $\lambda, \lambda' \in \Lambda$ with $\lambda \geq \lambda'$, we have $p^\lambda \cdot (R_I)^\sim \subseteq p^{\lambda'} \cdot (R_I)^\sim$.

(iii) *Suppose that $d_* = \max_{i \in I} \{d_i\}$ for some $*$ $\in I$. View $d_* \in \frac{1}{e_*} \mathbb{Z} \hookrightarrow \Lambda_I$ as an element $\vec{d}_* \in \Lambda_I$, and write*

$$\vec{d}_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (d_i)_{i \in I} \in \Lambda_I, \quad \vec{d}'_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \vec{d}_I - \vec{d}_* \in \Lambda_I,$$

$$d_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \deg(\vec{d}_I) = \sum_{i \in I} d_i, \quad d'_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \deg(\vec{d}'_I) = d_I - \max_{i \in I} \{d_i\}.$$

Then we have

$$p^{d'_I}(R_I)^\sim \subseteq R_I \subseteq (R_I)^\sim.$$

Proof. Assertions (i) and (ii) can be proved by definition. Assertion (iii) follows immediately from [38], Proposition 1.1. \square

Lemma 1.2. *Let k/k_0 be a finite extension of p -adic local fields. Let e, e_0 be the ramification indices of k and k_0 over \mathbb{Q}_p respectively. Let d, d_0 be the different indices [cf. §0] of k and k_0 respectively. Then:*

(i) *We have $d + \frac{1}{e} \geq d_0 + \frac{1}{e_0}$. Moreover, if k is tamely ramified over k_0 , then we have $d + \frac{1}{e} = d_0 + \frac{1}{e_0}$.*

(ii) *Suppose that k is a finite Galois extension of an intermediate subfield k_1 , such that k_1 is tamely ramified over k_0 . Then we have*

$$d \leq d_0 + \frac{1}{e_0} + v_p([k : k_1]).$$

(iii) *For the case of $k_0 = \mathbb{Q}_p$, we have:*

- *If $p \nmid e$, then $d = 1 - \frac{1}{e}$; if $e = 1$, then $d = 0$.*
- *If k is Galois over \mathbb{Q}_p , then $d \leq 1 + v_p(e)$.*

Proof. For assertions (i) and (ii), cf. [38], Proposition 1.3. For assertion (iii), we have $e_0 = 1, d_0 = 0$. Hence by (i), if $p \nmid e$, then $d = 1 - \frac{1}{e}$; if $e = 1$, then $d = 1 - \frac{1}{e} = 0$. Now suppose that k is Galois over \mathbb{Q}_p . Let k_1 be the maximal unramified subextension of k_0 in k , then k is Galois over k_1 , and we have $[k : k_1] = e$. Hence by (ii), we have $d \leq d_0 + \frac{1}{e_0} + v_p([k : k_1]) = 1 + v_p(e)$. \square

Lemma 1.3. *We continue to use the notation of Lemma 1.1. For each $i \in I$, define*

$$a_i \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{e_i} \cdot \left\lceil \frac{e_i + 1}{p - 1} \right\rceil, \quad b_i \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sup_{n \geq 0} \left\{ n - \frac{p^n}{e_i} \right\},$$

$$\vec{a}_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (a_i)_{i \in I}, \quad \vec{b}_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (b_i)_{i \in I} \in \Lambda_I, \quad a_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \deg(\vec{a}_I), \quad b_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \deg(\vec{b}_I).$$

Let

$$\phi : \log_p(R_I^\times) \xrightarrow{\sim} \log_p(R_I^\times)$$

be an automorphism of [finitely generated] \mathbb{Z}_p -module, which can be extended [by tensoring with \mathbb{Q}_p over \mathbb{Z}_p] to an automorphism of $R' = \mathbb{Q}_p \otimes_{\mathbb{Z}_p} \log_p(R_I^\times)$. Then:

(i) *For each $i \in I$, we have*

$$\pi_i^{a_i e_i} \mathcal{O}_{k_i} \subseteq \log_p(\mathcal{O}_{k_i}^\times) \subseteq \pi_i^{-b_i e_i} \mathcal{O}_{k_i}.$$

For each $\vec{\lambda} \in \Lambda_I$ with degree λ , we have

$$p^{\lambda + a_I} \cdot R_I \subseteq p^{\vec{\lambda}} \cdot \log_p(R_I^\times) \subseteq p^{\lambda - b_I} \cdot R_I.$$

(ii) *For each $\vec{\lambda} \in \Lambda_I$ with degree λ , we have*

$$\phi(p^\lambda \cdot (R_I)^\sim) \subseteq p^{\lfloor \lambda - d'_I - a_I \rfloor} \log_p(R_I^\times) \subseteq p^{\lfloor \lambda - d'_I - a_I \rfloor - b_I} \cdot (R_I)^\sim.$$

In particular, if $e_i \leq p - 2$ for each $i \in I$, then

$$\phi(p^\lambda \cdot (R_I)^\sim) \subseteq p^{\lambda - d'_I - 1} \cdot (R_I)^\sim.$$

(iii) We shall call $\mathcal{I}_{k_i} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{2p} \log_p(\mathcal{O}_{k_i}^\times) \subseteq k_i$ the log-shell of k_i for $i \in I$, and call

$$\mathcal{I}_{R'} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigotimes_{i \in I} \mathcal{I}_{k_i} = p^{-|I|} \cdot 2^{-|I|} \cdot \log_p(R_I^\times) \subseteq R'$$

the log-shell of R' , where the tensor product is over \mathbb{Z}_p . Then for each $\vec{\lambda} \in \Lambda_I$ with degree λ , we have

$$p^{\vec{\lambda}} \cdot \mathcal{I}_{R'} \subseteq p^{\lambda - b_I - v_p(2p) \cdot |I|} (R_I)^\sim.$$

Proof. First, to prove assertion (i), we only need to prove

$$\pi_i^{a_i e_i} \mathcal{O}_{k_i} \subseteq \log_p(\mathcal{O}_{k_i}^\times) \subseteq \pi_i^{-b_i e_i} \mathcal{O}_{k_i}$$

for each $i \in I$. On one hand, for each $x \in \pi_i^{a_i e_i} \mathcal{O}_{k_i}$, since $a_i = \frac{1}{e_i} \cdot \left\lceil \frac{e_i + 1}{p - 1} \right\rceil > \frac{1}{e_i} \cdot \frac{e_i}{p - 1} = \frac{1}{p - 1}$, we have $v_p(x) > \frac{1}{p - 1}$ and $x = \log_p(\exp_p(x)) \in \log_p(\mathcal{O}_{k_i}^\times)$. Hence $\pi_i^{a_i e_i} \mathcal{O}_{k_i} \subseteq \log_p(\mathcal{O}_{k_i}^\times)$. On the other hand, for each $x \in \pi_i \mathcal{O}_{k_i}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} v_p(\log_p(1 + x)) &= v_p\left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{m+1} \frac{x^m}{m}\right) \geq \inf_{m \geq 1} \left\{v_p\left(\frac{x^m}{m}\right)\right\} \\ &= -\sup_{m \geq 1} \{v_p(m) - m \cdot v_p(x)\} \geq -\sup_{n=v_p(m) \geq 0} \left\{n - \frac{p^n}{e_i}\right\} = -b_i. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\log_p(1 + x) \in \pi_i^{-b_i e_i} \mathcal{O}_{k_i}$. Then by the definition of p -adic logarithm, we have $\log_p(\mathcal{O}_{k_i}^\times) = \log_p(1 + \pi_i \mathcal{O}_{k_i}) \subseteq \pi_i^{-b_i e_i} \mathcal{O}_{k_i}$. This proves assertion (i).

Assertions (ii) and (iii) can be proved similarly to [the proof of] [38], Proposition 1.2. \square

Lemma 1.4. *We continue to use the notation of Lemma 1.3.*

(i) Recall that R' has a direct sum decomposition $R' = \bigoplus_{i=1}^{n_{R'}} L_i$, where L_i ($1 \leq i \leq n_{R'}$) are p -adic local fields. The log-volume functions on L_i [cf. [34], Proposition 5.7 (i)] determines a normalized log-volume function

$$\mu^{\log(-)}$$

defined on compact open subsets of R' , valued in \mathbb{R} , which is normalized so that

$$\mu^{\log}((R_I)^\sim) = 0, \quad \mu^{\log}(p(R_I)^\sim) = -\log(p).$$

(ii) For a subset $A \subseteq R'$, the holomorphic hull of A in R' is the smallest subset of the form $\bigoplus_{i=1}^{n_{R'}} x_i \mathcal{O}_{L_i} \subseteq R'$ which contains A , where x_i is a non-zero element of L_i for each $1 \leq i \leq n_{R'}$.

Suppose that $\vec{\lambda} \in \Lambda_I$ with degree λ . Let U be holomorphic hull of the union of $p^{\vec{\lambda}} \cdot \mathcal{I}_{R'}$ and $\phi(p^{\vec{\lambda}} \cdot (R_I)^\sim)$, where ϕ runs through all the automorphisms of the \mathbb{Q}_p -vector space R' which is extended by an automorphism of the \mathbb{Z}_p -module $\log_p(R_I^\times)$ (i.e. all the possible ϕ in Lemma 1.3). Then we have

$$\mu^{\log}(U) \leq (\max\{-\lambda + d'_I + a_I\}, -\lambda + v_p(2p) \cdot |I| + b_I) \cdot \log(p). \quad (1.1)$$

Proof. For assertion (i), cf. [38], Proposition 1.4. Next, we consider assertion (ii). Write

$$u \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\{\lceil -\lambda + d'_I + a_I \rceil, -\lambda + v_p(2p) \cdot |I|\} + b_I.$$

By Lemma 1.3 (ii), for each possible automorphism ϕ , we have

$$\phi(p^\lambda(R_I)^\sim) \subseteq p^{-(\lceil -\lambda + d'_I + a_I \rceil + b_I)}(R_I)^\sim \subseteq p^{-u} \cdot (R_I)^\sim.$$

And by Lemma 1.3 (iii), we have

$$p^{\vec{\lambda}} \cdot \mathcal{I}_{R'} \subseteq p^{-(\lceil -\lambda + b_I + v_p(2p) \cdot |I| \rceil)}(R_I)^\sim \subseteq p^{-u} \cdot (R_I)^\sim.$$

Since $p^{-u} \cdot (R_I)^\sim$ is of the form $\bigoplus_{i=1}^{n_{R'}} x_i \mathcal{O}_{L_i}$ [with each $x_i \in L_i$ satisfying $v_p(x_i) = -u$], U must be a subset of $p^{-u} \cdot (R_I)^\sim$ [by the definition of holomorphic hull]. Hence

$$\mu^{\log}(U) \leq \mu^{\log}(p^{-u} \cdot (R_I)^\sim) = u \cdot \log(p).$$

This proves assertion (ii). □

We also have a archimedean version of Lemma 1.4.

Lemma 1.5. *Let $\{k_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a finite set of complex archimedean local fields, where $|I| \geq 2$. For $i \in I$, write \mathcal{O}_{k_i} for the ring of integers of k_i . Then:*

(i) *Write $R' \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigotimes_{i \in I} k_i$, where the tensor product is over \mathbb{R} . Then we have a natural direct sum decomposition*

$$R' = \bigoplus_{i=1}^{n_{R'}} \mathbb{C}_i,$$

where $n_{R'} = 2^{|I|-1}$, and \mathbb{C}_i is a complex archimedean local field for each $1 \leq i \leq n_{R'}$. Write $B_I \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigoplus_{i=1}^{n_{R'}} \mathcal{O}_{\mathbb{C}_i}$, where $\mathcal{O}_{\mathbb{C}_i}$ is the unit ball of \mathbb{C}_i .

(ii) *The radial log-volume functions on \mathbb{C}_i [cf. [34], Proposition 5.7 (ii)] determines a normalized log-volume function*

$$\mu^{\log}(-)$$

defined on compact subsets of R' , valued in \mathbb{R} , which is normalized so that

$$\mu^{\log}(B_I) = 0, \quad \mu^{\log}(e \cdot B_I) = 1.$$

(iii) *We shall call $I_{k_i} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \pi \cdot \mathcal{O}_{k_i} \subseteq k_i$ the log-shell of k_i for $i \in I$. We shall write $I_{R'}$ for the image of $\prod_{i \in I} I_{k_i}$ in R' under the natural homomorphism $\prod_{i \in I} k_i \rightarrow \bigotimes_{i \in I} k_i = R'$, and call $I_{R'}$ the log-shell of R' .*

For a subset $A \subseteq R'$, the holomorphic hull of A in R' is the smallest subset of the form $\bigoplus_{i=1}^{n_{R'}} x_i \mathcal{O}_{\mathbb{C}_i} \subseteq R'$ which contains A , where x_i is a non-zero element of \mathbb{C}_i for each $1 \leq i \leq n_{R'}$.

Let U be holomorphic hull of the union of $\mathcal{I}_{R'}$ and B_I , Then we have

$$\mu^{\log}(U) \leq |I| \cdot \log(\pi).$$

Proof. For assertion (i), cf. [38], Proposition 1.5, where we can take $|V| = 1$. Assertion (ii) can be proved by definition. Assertion (iii) follows from the fact that $I_{R'}, B_I \subseteq \pi^{|I|} \cdot B_I$ and $\mu^{\log}(\pi^{|I|} \cdot B_I) = |I| \cdot \log(\pi)$, which can be verified by means of routine and elementary arguments. □

1.2 Estimation for Log-volumes of Initial Θ -Data

In this subsection, we will estimate the log-volumes associated to μ_6 -initial Θ -data [cf. [35], Definition 3.1 and [39], Definition 4.1]. We will maintain the notation throughout this subsection, and introduce additional notation as necessary to support our analysis.

The following lemma is helpful for constructing μ_6 -initial Θ -data.

Lemma 1.6. *Suppose that the following conditions are satisfied:*

- (a) F is a number field such that $\sqrt{-1} \in F$; \overline{F} is an algebraic closure of F . Write $G_F \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \text{Gal}(\overline{F}/F)$ for the absolute Galois group of F .
- (b) X_F is a punctured elliptic curve over F . Write E_F for the elliptic curve over F determined by X_F , then E_F is semi-stable and $F = F(E_F[6])$.
- (c) $F_{\text{mod}} \subseteq F$ is the field of moduli [cf., e.g., [34], Definition 5.1, (ii)] of X_F . Write

$$\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{V}(F_{\text{mod}}), \quad \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{non}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{V}(F_{\text{mod}})^{\text{non}}.$$

Then

$$\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}} \subseteq \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{non}}$$

is a nonempty set of nonarchimedean valuations of F_{mod} , such that E_F has bad multiplicative reduction at each $v \in \mathbb{V}(F)$ lying over $\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}$. Write

$$\mathbb{V}(F)^{\text{bad}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}} \times_{\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}} \mathbb{V}(F).$$

- (d) $l \geq 5$ is a prime number, such that the image of the Galois representation

$$\rho_{E_F, l} : G_F \rightarrow \text{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$$

determined by the l -torsion points of E_F contains the subgroup $\text{SL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l) \subseteq \text{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$. Write $K \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} F(E_F[l]) \subseteq \overline{F}$ for the l -torsion point field of E_F , then K is a finite Galois extension of F . Write $X_K \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} X_F \times_F K$, then X_K admits a K -core.

- (e) The field extension F/F_{mod} is Galois of degree prime to l . Also, for each $v \in \mathbb{V}(F)^{\text{bad}}$, l is prime to the residue characteristic of v , as well as to the order of the q -parameter of E_F at v .

Then there exists a section

$$\eta : \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}} \xrightarrow{\sim} \underline{\mathbb{V}} \subseteq \mathbb{V}(K)$$

of the natural surjection $\mathbb{V}(K) \rightarrow \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}$, a hyperbolic orbicurve \underline{C}_K of type $(1, l\text{-tors})_{\pm}$ [cf. [39], Definition 3.4, (i)] over K and a cusp $\underline{\epsilon}$ of \underline{C}_K , such that

$$(\overline{F}/F, X_F, l, \underline{C}_K, \underline{\mathbb{V}}, \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}, \underline{\epsilon})$$

is a μ_6 -initial Θ -data.

Proof. The lemma is a consequence of [35], Definition 3.1 and [39], Definition 4.1, where the existence of the section $\eta : \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}} \xrightarrow{\sim} \underline{\mathbb{V}}$ follows from the condition that the image of $\rho_{E_F, l}$ contains the subgroup $\text{SL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l) \subseteq \text{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$. \square

Definition 1.7. Suppose that $(\overline{F}/F, X_F, l, \underline{C}_K, \underline{\mathbb{V}}, \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}, \epsilon)$ is a μ_6 -initial Θ -data. We shall proceed with the notation of Lemma 1.6,

(i) For each $v \in \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{non}}$, we shall write $\underline{v} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \eta(v) \in \mathbb{V}(K)$, and write p_v for the residue characteristic of v , e_v for the ramification index of $K_{\underline{v}}$ over \mathbb{Q}_p , $d_v \in \frac{1}{e_v} \mathbb{Z}$ for the different index [cf. §0] of $K_{\underline{v}}$.

When $v \in \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}$, write q_v for the q -parameter of the Tate curve $E_{K_{\underline{v}}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E_F \times_F K_{\underline{v}}$, then by the fact that $2l$ -torsion points of E_F are defined over K and Proposition 2.1 (iv), we have

$$2l \mid \underline{v}(q_v) = e_v \cdot v_{p_v}(q_v). \quad (1.2)$$

When $v \notin \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}$, write $q_v \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1$, then $v_{p_v}(q_v) = 0$. Hence (1.2) is valid for every $v \in \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{non}}$.

We shall also write

$$a_v \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{e_v} \cdot \left\lceil \frac{e_v + 1}{p_v - 1} \right\rceil, \quad b_v \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sup_{n \geq 0} \left\{ n - \frac{p_v^n}{e_v} \right\}.$$

Then we have $a_v = -b_v = \frac{1}{e_v}$ when $e_v \leq p_v - 2$.

(ii) For each $v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}}$, we shall put

$$\log(\mathfrak{q}_{v_p}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{[F_{\text{mod}} : \mathbb{Q}]} \sum_{v \in (\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}})_{v_p}} \deg(v(q_v) \cdot v) \in \mathbb{R}.$$

We shall also write

$$\mathfrak{q} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{v \in \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{non}}} v(q_v) \cdot v \in \text{ADiv}_{\mathbb{R}}(\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}), \quad \log(\mathfrak{q}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \underline{\deg}_{F_{\text{mod}}}(\mathfrak{q}) \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Then

$$\log(\mathfrak{q}) = \frac{1}{[F_{\text{mod}} : \mathbb{Q}]} \sum_{v \in \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{non}}} \deg(v(q_v) \cdot v) = \sum_{v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}}} \log(\mathfrak{q}_{v_p}). \quad (1.3)$$

Definition 1.8. We shall proceed with the above notation. Suppose that $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, l^* = \frac{l-1}{2}\}$, $v_{\mathbb{Q}} \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}$.

(i) Let $v_0, v_1, \dots, v_j \in (\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}})_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}}$ be $j+1$ valuations. For $0 \leq i \leq j$, write $\underline{v}_i \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \eta(v_i) \in \underline{\mathbb{V}}$ and $k_i \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} K_{\underline{v}_i}$. We shall use $-|\log(\Theta)|_{(v_0, v_1, \dots, v_j)}$ to denote the log-volume of the following:

- For $v_{\mathbb{Q}} \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}}$, the holomorphic hull described in Lemma 1.4, where by (1.2) we can write $\vec{\lambda} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot \underline{v}_j(q_{v_j}) \in \frac{1}{e_{v_j}} \mathbb{Z} \hookrightarrow \bigoplus_{i=0}^j \frac{1}{e_{v_i}} \mathbb{Z}$.
- For $v_{\mathbb{Q}} \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{arc}}$, the holomorphic hull described in Lemma 1.5. In this case, since $\sqrt{-1} \in F \subseteq K$, all the k_i are complex archimedean local fields, which satisfies the premise of Lemma 1.5.

(ii) The weighted average log-volume $-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}, j}$ is defined by the formula

$$-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}, j} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{\sum_{v_0, \dots, v_j \in (\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}})_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}}} \left(\prod_{0 \leq i \leq j} [(F_{\text{mod}})_{v_i} : \mathbb{Q}_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}}] \right) \cdot \left(-|\log(\Theta)|_{(v_0, v_1, \dots, v_j)} \right)}{\sum_{v_0, \dots, v_j \in (\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}})_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}}} \left(\prod_{0 \leq i \leq j} [(F_{\text{mod}})_{v_i} : \mathbb{Q}_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}}] \right)}, \quad (1.4)$$

and the procession-normalized log-volume $-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}}$ is defined by the formula

$$-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{l^*} \sum_{1 \leq j \leq l^*} (-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{Q},j}}). \quad (1.5)$$

(iii) The log-volume of μ_6 -initial Θ -data $-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|$ is defined by the formula

$$-|\log(\underline{\Theta})| \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} - \sum_{v_{\mathbb{Q}} \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}} |\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{Q}}}. \quad (1.6)$$

Proposition 1.9. *Proceeding with the above notation, we have*

$$-\frac{1}{2l} \cdot \log(\mathfrak{q}) \leq -|\log(\underline{\Theta})|. \quad (1.7)$$

Proof. The proposition is a reformulation of the μ_6 -version of Corollary 3.12 of [37]. \square

From now on, we shall focus on the special case of $F_{\text{mod}} = \mathbb{Q}$, which is enough for the present paper. Then the j -invariant $j(E_F)$ of E_F is a rational number. For each $v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}}$, write $e_p \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} e_{v_p}$, $a_p \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} a_{v_p}$, $b_p \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} b_{v_p}$, $d_p \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} d_{v_p}$, $q_p \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} q_{v_p}$. Then $\log(\mathfrak{q}_{v_p}) = v_p(q_p) \cdot \log(p)$ for any prime number p , and by (1.3) we have

$$\log(\mathfrak{q}) = \sum_p v_p(q_p) \cdot \log(p). \quad (1.8)$$

Proposition 1.10. *Proceeding with the above notation, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{6} \log(\mathfrak{q}) &\leq \frac{l^2 + 5l}{l^2 + l - 12} \cdot (\log(\pi) + \sum_{p \geq 2} d_p \cdot \log(p) + \sum_{e_p \geq p-1} (\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_p}) \cdot \log(p) \\ &\quad + \sum_{e_p > p(p-1)} \log(\frac{e_p}{p-1})). \end{aligned} \quad (1.9)$$

Proof. By (1.6) and (1.7), we have

$$-\frac{1}{2l} \cdot \log(\mathfrak{q}) \leq -|\log(\underline{\Theta})| = (-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{R}}}) + \sum_{v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}}} (-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_p}), \quad (1.10)$$

where $v_{\mathbb{R}}$ is the unique real archimedean valuation on \mathbb{Q} .

We shall estimate $-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_p}$ at first. Let $v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}}$ and $1 \leq j \leq l^*$. Since $F_{\text{mod}} = \mathbb{Q}$, we have $(\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}})_{v_p} = \{v_p\}$. Then by (1.1) and (1.4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} -|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_p,j} &= -|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{\underbrace{(v_p, \dots, v_p)}_{j+1}} \leq (\max\{[-\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) + j \cdot d_p + (j+1) \cdot a_p], \\ &\quad -\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) + v_p(2p) \cdot (j+1)\} + (j+1)b_p) \cdot \log(p). \end{aligned} \quad (1.11)$$

By (1.2) we have $2l \mid e_p \cdot v_p(q_p)$, hence $-\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) \in \frac{1}{e_p} \mathbb{Z}$ and $-\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) + j \cdot d_p + (j+1) \cdot a_p \in \frac{1}{e_p} \mathbb{Z}$. Then since $d_p \geq 1 - \frac{1}{e_p}$ [cf. Lemma 1.2], we have

$$[-\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) + j \cdot d_p + (j+1) \cdot a_p] \leq -\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) + (j+1)(d_p + a_p). \quad (1.12)$$

Meanwhile, since $d_p \geq 1 - \frac{1}{e_p}$ and $a_p = \frac{1}{e_p} \cdot \left\lceil \frac{e_p+1}{p-1} \right\rceil \geq v_p(2) + \frac{1}{e_p}$, we have $d_p + a_p \geq v_p(2p)$, hence

$$-\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) + v_p(2p) \cdot (j+1) \leq -\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) + (j+1)(d_p + a_p). \quad (1.13)$$

By (1.11), (1.12) and (1.13), we have

$$-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_p, j} \leq \left(-\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) + (j+1)(d_p + a_p + b_p) \right) \cdot \log(p).$$

Then by averaging the cases $1 \leq j \leq l^*$ and by (1.5), we have

$$-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_p} \leq \left(-\frac{l+1}{24} \cdot v_p(q_p) + \frac{l+5}{4} \cdot (d_p + a_p + b_p) \right) \cdot \log(p). \quad (1.14)$$

Similarly, by combining Lemma 1.5 (iii) with Definition 1.8 (i), (ii), we can get

$$-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{R}}} \leq \frac{l+5}{4} \cdot \log(\pi).$$

Then by (1.10) and (1.14), we have

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{2l} \cdot \log(\mathfrak{q}) &\leq -|\log(\underline{\Theta})| = \sum_{v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}}} (-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_p} + (-|\log(\underline{\Theta})|_{v_{\mathbb{R}}})) \\ &\leq -\frac{l+1}{24} \cdot \sum_p v_p(q_p) \cdot \log(p) + \frac{l+5}{4} \cdot (\log(\pi) + \sum_p (d_p + a_p + b_p) \cdot \log(p)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence by (1.8) we have

$$\frac{1}{6} \log(\mathfrak{q}) \leq \frac{l^2 + 5l}{l^2 + l - 12} \cdot (\log(\pi) + \sum_{p \geq 2} (d_p + a_p + b_p) \cdot \log(p)). \quad (1.15)$$

To prove (1.9), we are left to estimate $a_p + b_p$. Recall that

$$a_p = \frac{1}{e_p} \cdot \left\lceil \frac{e_p+1}{p-1} \right\rceil \leq \frac{1}{p-1} + \frac{1}{e_p}, \quad b_p = \sup_{n \geq 0} \left\{ n - \frac{p^n}{e_p} \right\}.$$

Since $n - \frac{p^n}{e_p} \geq (n+1) - \frac{p^{n+1}}{e_p} \Leftrightarrow p^n \geq \frac{e_p}{p-1} \Leftrightarrow n \geq \log_p\left(\frac{e_p}{p-1}\right)$, when $n_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \lceil \log_p\left(\frac{e_p}{p-1}\right) \rceil \geq 1$, we have

$$b_p = n_0 - \frac{p^{n_0}}{e_p} \leq \log_p\left(\frac{e_p}{p-1}\right) + 1 - \frac{p}{e_p} \leq \frac{\log\left(\frac{e_p}{p-1}\right)}{\log(p)} + 1 - \frac{p}{e_p}.$$

When $e_p \leq p-2$, we have $a_p = -b_p = \frac{1}{e_p}$, hence $a_p + b_p = 0$; when $p-1 \leq e_p \leq p(p-1)$, we have $b_p = 1 - \frac{p}{e_p}$, hence $a_p + b_p \leq \frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_p}$; when $e_p > p(p-1)$, we have $a_p + b_p \leq \frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_p} + \frac{\log(e_p/(p-1))}{\log(p)}$. Hence by (1.15) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{6} \log(\mathfrak{q}) &\leq \frac{l^2 + 5l}{l^2 + l - 12} \cdot (\log(\pi) + \sum_{p \geq 2} d_p \cdot \log(p) + \sum_{e_p \geq p-1} \left(\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_p} \right) \cdot \log(p) \\ &\quad + \sum_{e_p > p(p-1)} \log\left(\frac{e_p}{p-1}\right)). \end{aligned}$$

□

1.3 Ramification datasets

We shall introduce the concept of ramification dataset. Ramification dataset encodes the ramification information of an initial Θ -data, which is useful for explicit computation.

Definition 1.11. A *ramification dataset* \mathfrak{R} consists of the following data:

- A prime number $l_0 \geq 5$ called base prime, an positive integer e_0 called base index.
- A non-empty finite set $S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}}$ of positive integers called the set of general multiplicative indices, such that every element in $S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}}$ equals e or $e \cdot l$, where $1 \leq e \leq e_0$ and $l \nmid e$.
- A finite set of prime numbers S_0 called the set of special primes.
- For each p in S_0 , a finite set S_p^{good} of positive integers called the set of good indices at p , and a finite set S_p^{multi} of positive integers called the set of multiplicative indices at p .

Definition 1.12. Let $\mathfrak{D} = (\overline{F}/F, X_F, l, \underline{C}_K, \underline{\mathbb{V}}, \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}, \epsilon)$ be a μ_6 -initial Θ -data such that $F_{\text{mod}} = \mathbb{Q}$, with ramification indices e_p defined as in the notation of Proposition 1.10. Let $\eta(v_p)$ be the valuation in $\underline{\mathbb{V}}$ lying over v_p , cf. Lemma 1.6.

(i) Write N for the denominator of the j -invariant $j(E_F) \in F_{\text{mod}} = \mathbb{Q}$ of the elliptic curve E_F associated to X_F . Then we shall say \mathfrak{D} is **of type** (l, N, N') if we have $\log(N') = \log(\mathfrak{q})$ for some positive integer N' .

(ii) We shall say \mathfrak{D} **admits** a ramification dataset \mathfrak{R} if in the notation of Definition 1.11, the following conditions hold:

- $l_0 = l$, i.e. l is the base prime of \mathfrak{R} .
- For each $p \notin S_0$, if E_K has good reduction at $\eta(v_p)$ [i.e. $p \nmid N$], then $e_p = 1$; if E_K has multiplicative reduction at $\eta(v_p)$ [i.e. $p \mid N$], then $e_p \in S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}}$.
- For each $p \in S_0$, if E_K has good reduction at $\eta(v_p)$ [i.e. $p \nmid N$], then $e_p \in S_p^{\text{good}}$; if E_K has multiplicative reduction at $\eta(v_p)$ [i.e. $p \mid N$], then $e_p \in S_p^{\text{multi}}$.

Corollary 1.13. Let \mathfrak{R} be a ramification dataset with base prime $l \geq 5$ and base index e_0 . Then there exists an algorithm [whose construction is presented in the proof] to compute a real number $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}) \geq 0$ that depends only on \mathfrak{R} , such that for any μ_6 -initial Θ -data \mathfrak{D} which admits \mathfrak{R} and is of type (l, N, N') , proceeding with the notation of Proposition 1.10, we have

$$\frac{1}{6} \log(N') \leq \frac{l^2 + 5l}{l^2 + l - 12} \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{e_0 l}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) - \frac{1}{e_0} \left(1 - \frac{1}{l}\right) \log \text{rad}(N_l) \right) + \text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}), \quad (1.16)$$

where $N_l \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p: l \mid v_p(N)} p^{v_p(N)}$.

Proof. We continue to use the notation of Proposition 1.10 and Definition 1.11. We shall provide an algorithm for computing the value of $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R})$:

Step 0: Let $p \leq e_0 l + 1$ be a prime number. When $p \notin S_0$, take $e = 1, \delta = 0$ or $e \in S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}}, \delta = 1$; when $p \in S_0$, take $e \in S_p^{\text{good}}, \delta = 0$ or take $e \in S_p^{\text{multi}}, \delta = 1$. Then we get finitely many triples (p, e, δ) .

Step 1: For each triple (p, e, δ) in step 0, we shall define several functions. Write $a_p(e) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{e} \cdot \left\lceil \frac{e+1}{p-1} \right\rceil$, $b_p(e) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sup_{n \geq 0} \left\{ n - \frac{p^n}{e} \right\}$. When $p \nmid e$, write $d_p(e) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1 - \frac{1}{e}$; when $p \mid e$,

write $d_p(e) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1 + v_p(e)$. When $\delta = 0$, take $u = 0$; when $\delta = 1$, let u be any integer such that $0 \leq u \leq 2l - 1$ and $2l \mid e \cdot u$. When $l \mid e$, write $l_0(e) = l$; when $l \nmid e$, write $l_0(e) = 1$. Then for $e \in S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}}$, we have $e \leq e_0 \cdot l_0(e)$. For each integer $1 \leq j \leq l^*$, define

$$\begin{aligned} B_0(p, e, \delta, u, j) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\left\{\left[-\frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot u + j \cdot d_p(e) + (j+1) \cdot a_p(e)\right] + \frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot u, v_p(2p) \cdot (j+1)\right\} \\ &\quad + (j+1) \cdot b_p(e), \\ B_1(p, e, \delta, u) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{l^*} \cdot \left(\sum_{j=1}^{l^*} B_0(p, e, \delta, u, j)\right) \cdot \frac{4}{l+5} - \left(1 - \frac{1}{e_0 \cdot l_0(e)}\right) \cdot \delta, \\ B_2(p) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max_{(e, \delta, u)} \{B_1(p, e, \delta, u)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Step 2: Finally, define $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R})$ by the equation

$$\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\left\{0, \frac{l^2 + 5l}{l^2 + l - 12} \cdot \left(\log(\pi) + \sum_{p \leq e_0 l + 1 \text{ or } p \in S} B_2(p) \cdot \log(p)\right)\right\}. \quad (1.17)$$

We claim that (1.16) is valid for the $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R})$ defined in this way. To show this, for each prime number p , we shall write $\delta_p = 0$ if $p \nmid N$, and write $\delta_p = 1$ if $p \mid N$. Recall that since $l \nmid [F : \mathbb{Q}]$, we can see that $l \mid e_p$ if and only if E_K has multiplicative reduction at $\eta(v)$ and $l \nmid v_p(N)$, which is equivalent to $(\frac{1}{l_0(e)} - \frac{1}{l}) \cdot \delta_p = (1 - \frac{1}{l})\delta_p \neq 0$. Hence

$$\log \text{rad}(N) = \sum_p \delta_p \log(p), \quad \left(1 - \frac{1}{l}\right) \log \text{rad}(N_l) = \sum_p \left(\frac{1}{l_0(e)} - \frac{1}{l}\right) \cdot \delta_p \log(p). \quad (1.18)$$

Write u_p for the remainder of $v_p(q_p)$ modulo p . Then we have $a_p = a_p(e_p)$, $b_p = b_p(e_p)$, $d_p \leq d_p(e_p)$; $\delta_p = 0$ (resp. $\delta_p = 1$) if and only if E_k has good (resp. multiplicative) reduction at $\eta(v_p)$; $u_p = 0$ when $\delta_p = 0$, and $2l \mid e_p \cdot u_p$ when $\delta_p = 1$. Hence (p, e_p, δ_p, u_p) is in the domain of the function $B_1(p, e, \delta, u)$.

Similar to the proof of Proposition 1.10, by (1.1) and (1.4), for $1 \leq j \leq l^*$, we have

$$-\left|\log(\underline{\Theta})\right|_{v_p, j} + \frac{j^2}{2l} \cdot v_p(q_p) \leq B_0(p, e_p, \delta_p, u_p, j) \cdot \log(p).$$

Then by averaging the cases $1 \leq j \leq l^*$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} -\left|\log(\underline{\Theta})\right|_{v_p} + \frac{l+1}{24} \cdot v_p(q_p) &\leq \frac{l+5}{4} \cdot \left(B_1(p, e_p, \delta_p, u_p) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{e_0 l_0(e)}\right) \delta_p\right) \cdot \log(p) \\ &\leq \frac{l+5}{4} \cdot \left(B_2(p) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{e_0 l}\right) \delta_p - \frac{1}{e_0} \left(\frac{1}{l_0(e)} - \frac{1}{l}\right) \delta_p\right) \cdot \log(p). \end{aligned}$$

Hence by summing over p and $v_{\mathbb{R}}$, and by (1.18) [cf. the proof of Proposition 1.10], we can get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{6} \log(\mathfrak{q}) &\leq \frac{l^2 + 5l}{l^2 + l - 12} \cdot \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{e_0 l}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) - \frac{1}{e_0} \left(1 - \frac{1}{l}\right) \log \text{rad}(N_l)\right) \\ &\quad + \log(\pi) + \sum_p B_2(p) \cdot \log(p). \end{aligned} \quad (1.19)$$

By (1.19) and the definition of $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R})$, to prove (1.16), it suffices to show that $B(p) = 0$ when $p \notin S_0$ and $p \geq e_0 l + 2 \geq 3$. For such p , consider all the possible $B_1(p, e, \delta, u)$.

Recall that since $p \notin S$, we have $e = 1, \delta = 0$ or $e \in S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}}, \delta = 1$.

When $e = 1, \delta = 0$, since $p \geq 3$, we have $a_p(e) = 1, b_p(e) = -1, d_p(e) = 0, u = 0, v_p(2p) = 1$. Hence $B_0(p, e, \delta, u, j) = 0$ and $B_1(p, e, \delta, u) = 0$.

When $e \in S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}}, \delta = 1$, since $p \geq e_0l + 2 \geq e + 2$, we have $a_p(e) = \frac{1}{e}, b_p(e) = -\frac{1}{e}, d_p(e) = 1 - \frac{1}{e}, v_p(2p) = 1$. Then similar to the proof of (1.14), we can show that

$$B_0(p, e, \delta, u, j) \leq \frac{l+5}{4} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{e}\right), \quad B_1(p, e, \delta, u) \leq \left(1 - \frac{1}{e}\right) - \left(1 - \frac{1}{e_0l_0(e)}\right) \leq 0.$$

Hence when $p \notin S$ and $p \geq e_0l + 2$, we have

$$B_2(p) = \max_{(e, \delta, u)} \{B_1(p, e, \delta, u)\} = 0.$$

This proves the corollary. \square

Remark 1.13.1. (i) Let \mathfrak{R} be the the ramification dataset in 1.13, and let p be a prime number. By taking $n = 0$, we have $b_p(e) \geq n - \frac{v^n}{e} = -\frac{1}{e}$, hence in the definition of $B_0(p, e, \delta, u, j)$, we have $B_0(p, e, \delta, u, j) \geq (j+1)(v_p(2p) + b_p(e)) \geq 0$. Then we have $B_1(p, e, \delta, u) \geq (\frac{1}{e_0l} - 1)\delta$ and $B_2(p) \geq \max_{(e, \delta, u)} \{(\frac{1}{e_0l} - 1)\delta\} \geq -1$.

Suppose that $p \notin S_0$, or S_p^{good} is not empty, then there exists a tuple (p, e, δ, u) in the domain of $B_1(p, e, \delta, u)$ with $\delta = 0$. Hence we have $B_2(p) \geq \max_{(e, \delta, u)} \{(\frac{1}{e_0l} - 1)\delta\} = 0$.

(ii) Suppose that S_0 is empty, or S_p^{good} is not empty for each $p \in S_0$. Then for each prime number p , we have $B_2(p) \geq 0$. Hence by (1.17) we have $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}) \geq \max\{0, \frac{l^2+5l}{l^2+l-12} \cdot \log(\pi)\} > \log(\pi)$.

Remark 1.13.2. (i) For each $p \notin S_0$, write $e_0(p) = e_0l$. For each $p \in S_0$, put

$$e_0(p) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max_{e \in S_p^{\text{good}} \cup S_p^{\text{multi}}} \{e\}, \quad d_0(p) = \max_{e \in S_p^{\text{good}} \cup S_p^{\text{multi}}} (1 + v_p(e)).$$

In addition, recall that for a proposition P , the Iverson Bracket is defined by $[P]_{\text{IB}} = 1$ if P is true, and $[P]_{\text{IB}} = 0$ if P is false.

Then by a similar approach to the proof of Proposition 1.10, we can show that

$$\begin{aligned} B_2(p) \cdot \log(p) &\leq [e_0(p) \geq p-1]_{\text{IB}} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_0(p)}\right) \cdot \log(p) \\ &\quad + [p \in S_0]_{\text{IB}} \cdot d_0(p) \cdot \log(p) + [e_0(p) > p(p-1)]_{\text{IB}} \cdot \log\left(\frac{e_0(p)}{p-1}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{1.20}$$

(ii) By a similar approach to the proof of Proposition 1.10, we can also show that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{l^2+l-12}{l^2+5l} \cdot \text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}) &\leq \log(\pi) + \sum_{e_0(p) \geq p-1} \left(\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_0(p)}\right) \cdot \log(p) \\ &\quad + \sum_{p \in S_0} d_0(p) \cdot \log(p) + \sum_{e_0(p) > p(p-1)} \log\left(\frac{e_0(p)}{p-1}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{1.21}$$

Remark 1.13.3. It is worth noting that the value of $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R})$ can be computed explicitly by the algorithm in the proof of Corollary 1.13. It is also worth noting that in the proof of each inequality in this section, the condition that 3-torsion points of E_F are defined over F is not used.

2 Construction of initial Θ -Data

In this section, we will prove a local version of effective abc-type inequalities associated to the triples (a, b, c) , where a, b, c are non-zero coprime integers such that

$$a + b = c.$$

2.1 The general construction

We shall provide a procedure for constructing μ_6 -initial Θ -data from an elliptic curve defined over \mathbb{Q} . Some results in the arithmetic of elliptic curves are needed for the construction.

Proposition 2.1. *Let K be a number field, E be an elliptic curve defined over K , $j(E) \in K$ be the j -invariant of E . Let $w \in \mathbb{V}(L)$ be a nonarchimedean valuation of L lying over some $v \in \mathbb{V}(K)^{\text{non}}$, with residue characteristic p . Then:*

(i) *For any integer $n \geq 2$, the n -torsion point field $K(E[n])$ is Galois over K ; we have $\mu_n \subseteq K(E[n])$, where μ_n denotes the group of n -th roots of 1 in $\overline{\mathbb{Q}}$; if $m, n \geq 2$ are coprime integers, then $K(E[mn]) = K(E[m], E[n])$, $K(E[m]) \cap K(E[n]) = K$.*

(ii) *Suppose that $l \geq 3$ is a prime number, $l \neq p$, and all the l -torsion points of E are defined over K_v [i.e. $K_v = K_v(E[l])$]. Then E has semi-stable reduction at v .*

(iii) *Suppose that E has good reduction at v . If $l \neq p$, then the field extension L_w/K_v is unramified; if $l = p$ and v is not ramified over \mathbb{Q} , then the ramification index of the field extension L_w/K_v belongs to the set $\{l - 1, l(l - 1), l^2 - 1\}$.*

(iv) *Suppose that E has bad multiplicative reduction at v , $n \geq 2$ is an integer. Write q_K for the q -parameter of $E_{K_v} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \times_K K_v$, e_v for the ramification index of the field extension $K(E[n])/K$ at v . Then we have $v(q_K) = -v(j(E))$, and there exists an unramified field extension L/K_v of degree 1 or 2, such that $L(E[n]) = L(\mu_n, q_K^{1/n})$. Hence if $p \nmid n$, then the field extension $K_v(E[n])/K_v$ is tamely ramified, and $e_v = n/\gcd(v(q_K), n)$; if $v_p(n) = 1$ and the field extension K_v/\mathbb{Q}_p is unramified, then $e_v = (p - 1) \cdot n/\gcd(v(q_K), n)$.*

(v) *The field of moduli [cf., e.g., [34], Definition 5.1, (ii)] of E is the field generated over \mathbb{Q} by the j -invariant $j(E)$ of E . If there exists a prime number $l \geq 3$, such that all the l -torsion points of E are defined over K , then any model of $E_{\overline{K}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \times_K \overline{K}$ over K is isomorphic to E , hence any model of $E_{\overline{K}}$ over its field of moduli is also a model of E .*

Proof. For assertion (i), cf. [1], Proposition 5.2.1 and Proposition 5.2.2. For assertion (ii), cf. [38], Proposition 1.8 (v). For assertion (iii), cf. [11], §7.4 Theorem 5 and the introduction of [43]. Assertion (iv) follows from the theory of Tate curves, cf. [47], §5 for a reference. Assertion (v) follows from [38], Proposition 1.8 (ii), (iv). \square

Proposition 2.2. *Let E be an elliptic curve defined over a number field K , X be the punctured elliptic curve [defined over K] associated to E . Suppose that*

$$j(E) \notin \{0, 2^6 \cdot 3^3, 2^2 \cdot 73^3 \cdot 3^{-4}, 2^{14} \cdot 31^3 \cdot 5^{-3}\},$$

then X admits a K -core [cf. [32], remark 2.1.1].

Proof. The proposition follows immediately from [44], Table 4 [cf. also [44], Lemma 1.1.1; [32], Proposition 2.7]. \square

Proposition 2.3. *Let E be an elliptic curve defined over \mathbb{Q} with j -invariant $j(E) \in \mathbb{Q}$, l be a prime number. Suppose that (a) $l \geq 23$ and $l \neq 37, 43, 67, 163$; or (b) E is semi-stable and $l \geq 11$; or (c) $l \geq 11$, $l \neq 13$ and the denominator of $j(E)$ is not a power of 2. Then E doesn't admit a \mathbb{Q} -rational isogeny of degree l .*

Proof. The proposition follows immediately from [30], Theorem 1, Theorem 4 and Corollary 4.4. \square

Corollary 2.4. *Let E be an elliptic curve defined over \mathbb{Q} , l be a prime number. Let p be a prime number, such that $v_p(j(E)) < 0$ and $l \nmid v_p(j(E))$. Suppose that (a) $l \geq 23$ and $l \neq 37, 43, 67, 163$; or (b) E is semi-stable and $l \geq 11$; or (c) $l \geq 11$, $l \neq 13$ and the denominator of $j(E)$ is not a power of 2. Then the the mod- l Galois representation $\rho = \rho_{E,l} : G_{\mathbb{Q}} \rightarrow \mathrm{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$ associated to E is a surjection.*

Proof. Write H for the image $\rho(G_{\mathbb{Q}}) \subseteq \mathrm{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$. By taking into account that the determinant of the image of ρ is \mathbb{F}_l^{\times} , we only need to prove that $\mathrm{SL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l) \subseteq H$.

Since $v_p(j(E)) < 0$, E has potentially bad multiplicative reduction at p . Hence there exists a p -adic local field k , such that $[k : \mathbb{Q}_p] \mid 2$, and $E_k \stackrel{\mathrm{def}}{=} E \times_{\mathbb{Q}} k$ has bad multiplicative reduction. Since $l \nmid v_p(j(E))$, it follows from the discussion of the local theory preceding [33], Lemma 3.2 that the image H contains [up to conjugacy] the element $\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathrm{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$.

Since (a) or (b) or (c) is true, by Lemma 2.3, E doesn't admit a \mathbb{Q} -rational isogeny of degree l . Hence H is not contained in the Borel subgroup $\begin{pmatrix} * & \\ 0 & * \end{pmatrix} \subseteq \mathrm{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$, so H contains at least one matrix that is not upper triangular. Then by [33], Lemma 3.1 (iii), we have $\mathrm{SL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l) \subseteq H$. \square

Now we shall start the construction of μ_6 -initial Θ -data.

Proposition 2.5. *Let E be an elliptic curve defined over \mathbb{Q} with j -invariant $j(E) \in \mathbb{Q}$; N be the denominator of $j(E)$; F be a number field which is Galois over \mathbb{Q} ; $l \geq 5$ be a prime number such that $l \nmid [F : \mathbb{Q}]$; X_F be the punctured elliptic curve associated to $E_F \stackrel{\mathrm{def}}{=} E \times_{\mathbb{Q}} F$. Suppose that:*

- (a) $\sqrt{-1} \in F$, $F(E[6]) = F$, E_F is semi-stable, and $F \subseteq \mathbb{Q}(E[n])$ for some positive integer $l \nmid n$.
- (b) $j(E) \notin \{0, 2^6 \cdot 3^3, 2^2 \cdot 73^3 \cdot 3^{-4}, 2^{14} \cdot 31^3 \cdot 5^{-3}\}$.
- (c) We have $l \geq 23$ and $l \neq 37, 43, 67, 163$; or E is semi-stable and $l \geq 11$; or $l \geq 11$, $l \neq 13$ and N is not a power of 2.
- (d) We have $N'_l \neq 1$, where $N'_l \stackrel{\mathrm{def}}{=} \prod_{p:p \neq l, l \nmid v_p(N)} p^{v_p(N)}$.

Then there exists a μ_6 -initial Θ -data

$$\mathfrak{D}(E, F, l, \mu_6) = (\overline{F}/F, X_F, l, \underline{C}_K, \underline{\mathbb{V}}, \mathbb{V}_{\mathrm{mod}}^{\mathrm{bad}}, \underline{\epsilon}),$$

which is of type (l, N, N'_l) [cf. the notation in Definition 1.12, (i)].

Proof. The proof will be shown by making use of Lemma 1.6.

(1) Write $F_{\mathrm{mod}} \stackrel{\mathrm{def}}{=} \mathbb{Q}$, then F is Galois over F_{mod} , $l \nmid [F : F_{\mathrm{mod}}]$. By (a), we have $\sqrt{-1} \in F$, 6-torsion points of E_F are rational over F , and E_F is semi-stable. Let \overline{F} be an algebraic closure of F , write $G_F \stackrel{\mathrm{def}}{=} \mathrm{Gal}(\overline{F}/F)$ for the absolute Galois group of F .

(2) Let X be the punctured elliptic curve defined over \mathbb{Q} associated to E , then $X_F = X \times_{\mathbb{Q}} F$. Hence the field of moduli of X_F is $\mathbb{Q} = F_{\text{mod}}$. By (a), the elliptic curve E_F is semi-stable. Write

$$\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{V}(F_{\text{mod}}) = \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}, \quad \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\mathbb{Q}}^{\text{non}} : p \neq l, l \nmid v_p(N)\}.$$

Then since $N'_l \neq 1$ by (d), $\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}$ is a nonempty set of nonarchimedean valuations of F_{mod} .

(3) For each $v \in \mathbb{V}(F)$ lying over some $v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}$, we have $p \neq l$ and $l \nmid v_p(N) = v_p(q_p)$, where q_p is the q -parameter of E at v_p . Write e' for the ramification index of F_v over \mathbb{Q}_p . Since $l \nmid [F : \mathbb{Q}]$, $e' \mid [F : \mathbb{Q}]$, we have $l \nmid e'$. Then since $l \nmid v_p(N) = v_p(q_p)$, we have $l \nmid e' \cdot v_p(q_p) = v(q_p)$. Hence for each $v \in \mathbb{V}(F)^{\text{bad}} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}} \times_{\mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}} \mathbb{V}(F)$, l is prime to the residue characteristics of v , as well as to the order of the q -parameter of E_F at v .

(4) By Corollary 2.4 and (c), the mod- l Galois representation $\rho_{E,l} : G_{\mathbb{Q}} \rightarrow \text{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$ associated to E is a surjection. Note that since $F \subseteq \mathbb{Q}(E[n])$ and $l \nmid n$ by (a), we have $F \cap \mathbb{Q}(E[l]) = \mathbb{Q}$ by Lemma 2.1, (i). Hence the image of the mod- l Galois representation $\rho_{E_F,l}$ [associated to E_F] equals the image of $\rho_{E,l}$ [which equals $\text{GL}(2, \mathbb{F}_l)$], thus $\rho_{E_F,l}$ is a surjection.

(5) Write $K \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} F(E_F[l]) \subseteq \overline{F}$ for the l -torsion point field of E_F . Then since F and $\mathbb{Q}(E[l])$ are Galois over $F_{\text{mod}} = \mathbb{Q}$, the field $K = F \cdot \mathbb{Q}(E[l])$ is a finite Galois extension of F_{mod} . Write $X_K \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} X_F \times_F K$, then by Proposition 2.2 and (b), X_K admits a K -core.

Now by the above facts (1)–(5), the existence of the μ_6 -initial Θ -data $\mathfrak{D}(E, F, l, \mu_6)$ follows from Lemma 1.6, and $\log(\mathfrak{q}) = \log(N'_l)$ follows easily from Definition 1.7. \square

2.2 The consturction for Frey-Hellegouarch curves

Let (a, b, c) be a triple of non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b = c$. The Frey-Hellegouarch curve associated to (a, b, c) is the elliptic curve defined over \mathbb{Q} by the equation

$$y^2 = x(x - a)(x + b).$$

This curve is popularized in its application to Fermat's Last Theorem, where one investigates a (hypothetical) solution to the Fermat equation $x^l + y^l = z^l$.

Lemma 2.6. *Let (a, b, c) be a triple of non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b = c$; E be the Frey-Hellegouarch curve associated to (a, b, c) , which is defined over \mathbb{Q} by the equation $y^2 = x(x - a)(x + b)$. Let $l \geq 5$ be a prime number.*

(i) *By Tate's algorithm, we have*

$$c_4(E) = 16(a^2 + ab + b^2), \quad \Delta(E) = 16a^2b^2c^2, \quad j(E) = \frac{256(a^2 + ab + b^2)^3}{a^2b^2c^2} \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

For each prime number $p \neq 2$, the Frey-Hellegouarch curve E has good reduction at v_p when $p \nmid abc$, and has multiplicative reduction at v_p when $p \mid abc$. Moreover, if $4 \mid (a + 1)$ and $16 \mid b$, then E is semi-stable.

(ii) *Write $F \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-1}, E[3])$, then F is Galois over \mathbb{Q} , $F = F(E[6])$, E_F is semi-stable, and $F \subseteq \mathbb{Q}(E[12])$. Write*

$$N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{|abc|}{\gcd(16, abc)}, \quad N'_l \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p:p \neq l, l \nmid v_p(N)} p^{v_p(N)}.$$

Then N^2 is the denominator of $j(E)$, $v_2(N) = \max\{v_2(abc) - 4, 0\}$, and we have $v_p(N) = v_p(abc)$ for each prime number $p \geq 3$. Write X_F for the punctured elliptic curve associated to $E_F \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \times_F F$.

(iii) Suppose that $N'_l \neq 1$ and $(|a|, |b|, |c|)$ is not a permutation of $(1, 1, 2)$, $(1, 8, 9)$. Also, suppose that (a) $l \geq 11$ and $l \neq 13$; or (b) $l \geq 11$, $4 \mid (a+1)$ and $16 \mid b$.

Then by Proposition 2.5, there exists a μ_6 -initial Θ -data

$$\mathfrak{D}(E, F, l, \mu_6) = (\overline{F}/F, X_F, l, \underline{C}_K, \underline{V}, \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{bad}}, \underline{\epsilon}),$$

which is of type $(l, N^2, (N'_l)^2)$.

(iv) In the situation of (iii), proceeding with the notation in §1. For each $v_p \in \mathbb{V}_{\text{mod}}^{\text{non}}$, write e_p for the ramification index of $K_{\eta(v)}$ over \mathbb{Q}_p , d_p for the different index of $K_{\eta(v)}$. Then:

- When $p \mid abc$ and $p \neq 2$, E has multiplicative reduction at v_p . In this case, if $p \neq 3, l$, then $e_p = 6l / \gcd(v_p(N^2), 6l) = 3l / \gcd(v_p(abc), 3l)$ divides $3l$, $p \nmid e_p$, $d_p = 1 - \frac{1}{e_p} \leq 1 - \frac{1}{3l}$; if $p \in \{3, l\}$, then $e_p = 3l(p-1) / \gcd(v_p(abc), 3l)$, hence $e_3 \in \{2, 6, 2l, 6l\}$, $e_l \in \{l-1, 3(l-1), l(l-1), 3l(l-1)\}$, $d_3 \leq 2$, $d_l \leq 2$.
- When $p \mid abc$ and $p \neq 2$, E has good reduction at v_p . In this case, if $p \neq 3, l$, then $e_p = 1$, $d_p = 0$; if $p \in \{3, l\}$, then $e_3 \in \{2, 6, 8\}$, $e_l \in \{l-1, l(l-1), l^2-1\}$, $d_3 \leq 2$, $d_l \leq 2$.
- Note that $v_2(abc) \geq 1$. When $v_2(abc) \geq 5$, $E' \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E \times_{\mathbb{Q}} \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-1})$ has multiplicative reduction at the unique valuation of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-1})$ lying over v_2 , then $e_2 = 6l / \gcd(v_2(abc) - 4, 3l)$, $e_2 \in \{2, 6, 2l, 6l\}$, $d_2 \leq 2$; when $v_2(abc) = 4$, E has good reduction at v_2 , then $e_2 = 2$, $d_2 \leq 2$; when $1 \leq v_2(abc) \leq 3$, E has potentially good reduction at v_2 , we have $2 \mid e_2$, $e_2 \mid 48$ and $d_2 \leq 1 + v_2(e_2) \leq 5$.

Proof. For assertion (i), the case $p \neq 2$ follows from Tate's algorithm. When $4 \mid (a+1)$ and $16 \mid b$, by the change of variables $x \mapsto 4x$, $y \mapsto 8y + 4x$, E can be defined by the new equation

$$E' : y^2 + xy = x^3 + \frac{b-a-1}{4} \cdot x^2 - \frac{ab}{16} \cdot x.$$

By Tate's algorithm, we can show that

$$c_4(E') = a^2 + ab + b^2, \quad \Delta(E') = 2^{-8} a^2 b^2 c^2, \quad j(E') = \frac{(a^2 + ab + b^2)^3}{2^{-8} a^2 b^2 c^2}.$$

Then since $\gcd(c_4(E'), \Delta(E')) = 1$, E' is semi-stable, so E is semi-stable.

Assertion (ii) is a consequence of Proposition 2.1 and Proposition 2.2.

For assertion (iii), since $(|a|, |b|, |c|)$ is not a permutation of $(1, 1, 2)$, $(1, 8, 9)$, we have $j(E) \notin \{0, 2^6 \cdot 3^3, 2^2 \cdot 73^3 \cdot 3^{-4}, 2^{14} \cdot 31^3 \cdot 5^{-3}\}$, and N is not a power of 2. Then assertion (iii) follows easily from Proposition 2.5.

Assertion (iv) can be proved via Lemma 1.2, Proposition 2.1 and assertions (i), (ii). We shall prove the case of $p = 2$, $1 \leq v_2(abc) \leq 3$ as an example. In this case, $v_2(N) = 0$, thus E has potentially good reduction at v_2 . Since $\sqrt{-1} \in F \subseteq K$, we have $2 \mid e_2$. Let $v' \in \mathbb{V}(F)$ be the image of $\underline{v} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \eta(v_2)$ via the surjection $\mathbb{V}(K) \twoheadrightarrow \mathbb{V}(F)$. By Proposition 2.1, E_F has good reduction at v' , thus the extension $K_{\underline{v}}/F_{v'}$ is unramified. Then since $\mathbb{Q} \subseteq \mathbb{Q}(\mu_3) \subseteq F = \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-1}, E[3])$ and $\mathbb{Q}(\mu_3)/\mathbb{Q}$ is unramified at v_2 , we have $e_2 \mid [F : \mathbb{Q}(\mu_3)] \mid 48$, and hence $d_2 \leq 1 + v_2(e_2) \leq 5$ by Lemma 1.2. \square

Proposition 2.7. *Let (a, b, c) be a triple of non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b = c$, $l \geq 11$ be a prime number. Write $N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |abc| / \gcd(16, abc)$. Suppose that (a) $l \neq 13$; or (b) $16 \mid abc$.*

Let \mathfrak{R}_l be the ramification dataset consists of the following data:

$$\begin{aligned} l_0 &= l, \quad e_0 = 3, \quad S_0 = \{2, 3, l\}, \quad S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}} = \{1, 3, l, 3l\}, \quad S_2^{\text{good}} = \{e : e \mid 48, 2 \mid e\}, \\ S_3^{\text{good}} &= \{2, 6, 8\}, \quad S_l^{\text{good}} = \{l-1, l(l-1), l^2-1\}, \quad S_2^{\text{multi}} = \{2, 6, 2l, 6l\}, \\ S_3^{\text{multi}} &= \{2, 6, 2l, 6l\}, \quad S_l^{\text{multi}} = \{l-1, 3(l-1), l(l-1), 3l(l-1)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then with $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l)$ defined in Corollary 1.13, we have

$$\log(N) \leq \left(3 + \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + 3 \text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l) + \sum_{p: p=l \text{ or } l \mid v_p(N)} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p). \quad (2.1)$$

Proof. Write $N'_l \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p: p \neq l, l \nmid v_p(N)} p^{v_p(N)}$. Then it suffices to show that

$$\frac{1}{3} \log(N'_l) \leq \left(1 + \frac{11l + 31}{3l^2 + 3l - 36}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + \text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l). \quad (2.2)$$

When $N'_l = 1$ or $(|a|, |b|, |c|)$ is a permutation of $(1, 1, 2)$, $(1, 8, 9)$, we have $\frac{1}{3} \log(N'_l) < \log(3) < \log(\pi)$. Then (2.2) follows from $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l) > \log(\pi) > \frac{1}{3} \log(N'_l)$ by Remark 1.13.1. Hence we can assume that $N'_l \neq 1$ and $(|a|, |b|, |c|)$ is not a permutation of $(1, 1, 2)$, $(1, 8, 9)$.

In the case (b) where $16 \mid abc$, since (2.2) is symmetric for (a, b, c) , we can assume that $16 \mid b$. Then if $4 \nmid a$, we can replace (a, b, c) by $(-a, -b, -c)$, thus we can assume that $4 \mid (a+1)$. Hence we can assume that (a) $l \neq 13$; or (b) $4 \mid (a+1)$ and $16 \mid b$.

Then by Lemma 2.6, (iii), there exists a μ_6 -initial Θ -data $\mathfrak{D} = \mathfrak{D}(E, F, l, \mu_6)$, which is of type $(l, N^2, (N'_l)^2)$. Moreover, by Lemma 2.6, (iv) and Definition 1.12, \mathfrak{D} admits \mathfrak{R}_l . Then (2.2) follows directly from Corollary 1.13. \square

Remark 2.7.1. When we have $16 \mid abc$ in Proposition 2.7, we can define the ramification dataset \mathfrak{R}'_l by defining $S_2^{\text{good}} = \{2\}$ instead in the definition of \mathfrak{R}_l . Then similar to the proof of Proposition 2.7, we have

$$\log(N) \leq \left(3 + \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + 3 \text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}'_l) + \sum_{p: p=l \text{ or } l \mid v_p(N)} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p).$$

2.3 Effective partial abc inequalities

We shall call (2.1) the partial abc inequality. In this subsection, we will prove an effective version of (2.1) by estimating the term $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l)$. The following lemma in analytic number theory is needed, where the ‘‘sum over p ’’ runs over prime numbers.

Lemma 2.8. (i) *For real number $x > 3$, put*

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{\log(p)}{p-1} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{x}\right) \cdot \sum_{p \leq x} \log(p) - \frac{1}{x} \sum_{p \leq x} p \cdot \log(p) + \sum_{p < \sqrt{x+1}} \log\left(\frac{x}{p-1}\right) \\ f_2(x) &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{x^2 + 5x}{x^2 + x - 12} \cdot \left(f_1(3x) + \frac{10}{3} \cdot \log(x) + 9\right). \end{aligned}$$

Then for integer $n \geq 2 \cdot 10^5$, we have

$$f_2(n) < \frac{3}{2} \cdot n + 0.06 \cdot \frac{n}{\log(n)}.$$

(ii) For real number $x \geq 1$, write

$$S_x \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{p \in \mathfrak{Primes} : \sqrt{x/\log(2)} < p \leq \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{x\log(x)}\},$$

$$f_3(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |S_x|, \quad f_4(x) = \sum_{p \in S_x} p.$$

Then for any real number $x \geq e^{31}$, we have

$$f_3(x) \geq \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{x} \cdot (\sqrt{\log(x)} - 2.14)}{\log(x) + \log \log(x)}, \quad f_4(x) < \frac{4}{9}x \cdot \left(1 + \frac{4.33}{\log(x)}\right).$$

Proof. Write $\pi(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{p \leq x} 1$ for the prime counting function and write $\vartheta(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{p \leq x} \log(p)$ for the first Chebyshev function.

First, we consider assertion (i). We shall use the Stieltjes integral.

By [24], Section 4, we have

$$|\vartheta(x) - x| \leq \epsilon \cdot \frac{x}{\log(x)} \quad \text{for } x \geq A, \quad (2.3)$$

where $A = 2.89 \cdot 10^7$, $\epsilon = 0.006788$. Then by (2.3), for $x \geq A$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{A < p \leq x} p \cdot \log(p) &= \int_A^x t \cdot d(\vartheta(t)) = [t \cdot \vartheta(t)]_A^x - \int_A^x \vartheta(t) dt \\ &\geq x \cdot \vartheta(x) - A \cdot \vartheta(A) - \int_A^x \left(t + \epsilon \cdot \frac{\log(A)}{2 \log(A) - 1} \cdot \frac{2t \log(t) - t}{\log^2(t)}\right) dt \\ &\geq x \cdot \vartheta(x) - A \cdot \vartheta(A) - \int_A^x \left(t + 0.515\epsilon \cdot \frac{2t \log(t) - t}{\log^2(t)}\right) dt \\ &\geq \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon}{\log(x)}\right)x^2 - \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon}{\log(A)}\right)A^2 - \left[\frac{t^2}{2} + \frac{0.515\epsilon t^2}{\log(t)}\right]_A^x \\ &\geq \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1.515\epsilon}{\log(x)}\right)x^2 - \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{0.485\epsilon}{\log(A)}\right)A^2. \end{aligned}$$

For $x \geq 10 \cdot A$, the computation in [50] shows that

$$\sum_{p \leq A} p \cdot \log(p) - \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{0.485\epsilon}{\log(A)}\right)A^2 > -\frac{0.008\epsilon \cdot (10 \cdot A)^2}{\log(10 \cdot A)} \geq -\frac{0.008\epsilon x^2}{\log(x)}.$$

Hence for $x \geq 10 \cdot A$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \leq x} p \cdot \log(p) &= \sum_{A < p \leq x} p \cdot \log(p) + \sum_{p \leq A} p \cdot \log(p) \\ &\geq \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1.523\epsilon}{\log(x)}\right)x^2 - \frac{0.008\epsilon x^2}{\log(x)} = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1.523\epsilon}{\log(x)}\right)x^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

By [42], Equation (3.24), we have

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{\log(p)}{p} < \log(x) \quad \text{for } x > 1.$$

Thus by the computation in [50], we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{\log(p)}{p-1} &= \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{\log(p)}{p} + \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{\log(p)}{p(p-1)} < \log(x) + \sum_{p \leq A} \frac{\log(p)}{p(p-1)} + \sum_{n > A} \frac{\log(n)}{n(n-1)} \\ &< \log(x) + \sum_{p \leq A} \frac{\log(p)}{p(p-1)} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{A}} < \log(x) + 0.8. \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

By [42], Equation (3.14), (3.29), for $x \geq 10 \cdot A > \exp(19.48)$, we have $\vartheta(\sqrt{x}) > \sqrt{x} \cdot (1 - \frac{1}{\log(x)}) > 0.94\sqrt{x}$, and $\sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x+1}} \log(\frac{p}{p-1}) \leq \log(e^\gamma \log(\sqrt{x+1})(1 + \frac{1}{2\log(\sqrt{x+1})})) < \log \log(\sqrt{x+1}) + 0.63 < \log \log(x)$, where $\gamma = 0.57721 \dots$ is Euler's constant. Hence for $x \geq 10 \cdot A$, we have

$$\sum_{p < \sqrt{x+1}} \log(\frac{1}{p-1}) \leq \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{x+1}} \log(\frac{p}{p-1}) - \vartheta(\sqrt{x}) < \log \log(x) - 0.94\sqrt{x}. \quad (2.6)$$

By [25], Corollary 5.2, for $x > 1$ we have

$$\frac{x}{\log(x)} \underset{x \geq 17}{\leq} \pi(x) \underset{x > 1}{\leq} \frac{x}{\log(x)} (1 + \frac{1}{\log(x)} + \frac{2.53816}{\log^2(x)}) \underset{x \geq e^{31}}{\leq} \frac{x}{\log(x)} (1 + \frac{1.082}{\log(x)}). \quad (2.7)$$

Then for $x \geq 10 \cdot A > \exp(19.48)$, we have $\sum_{p < \sqrt{x+1}} \log(x) \leq (\pi(\sqrt{x}) + 1) \cdot \log(x) \leq 2\sqrt{x}(1 + \frac{1}{\log(\sqrt{x})} + \frac{2.53816}{\log^2(\sqrt{x})}) + \log(x) < 2.26\sqrt{x}$. Hence by (2.6), $\sum_{p < \sqrt{x+1}} \log(\frac{x}{p-1}) = \sum_{p < \sqrt{x+1}} \log(x) + \sum_{p < \sqrt{x+1}} \log(\frac{1}{p-1}) < 2.26\sqrt{x} + \log \log(x) - 0.94\sqrt{x} = 1.32\sqrt{x} + \log \log(x)$. Then by (2.3), (2.4) and (2.5), for $x \geq 10 \cdot A$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x) &= \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{\log(p)}{p-1} + (1 + \frac{1}{x})\vartheta(x) - \frac{1}{x} \sum_{p \leq x} p \cdot \log(p) + \sum_{p < \sqrt{x+1}} \log(\frac{x}{p-1}) \\ &< \log(x) + 0.8 + (1 + \frac{1}{x}) \cdot x \cdot (1 + \frac{\epsilon}{\log(x)}) - \frac{1}{x} \cdot (\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1.523\epsilon}{\log(x)}) \cdot x^2 + 1.32\sqrt{x} + \log \log(x) \\ &< \frac{1}{2} \cdot x + 0.01865 \cdot \frac{x}{\log(x)}. \end{aligned}$$

The computation in [50] shows that $f_1(n) < \frac{1}{2} \cdot n + 0.01865 \cdot \frac{n}{\log(n)}$ holds for any integer $2 \cdot 10^5 \leq n \leq 10 \cdot A$. Hence for any integer $n \geq 2 \cdot 10^5$, we have

$$f_1(n) < \frac{1}{2} \cdot n + 0.01865 \cdot \frac{n}{\log(n)}.$$

Then for any integer $n \geq 2 \cdot 10^5$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} f_2(n) &= \frac{n^2 + 5n}{n^2 + n - 12} \cdot (f_1(3n) + \frac{10}{3} \cdot \log(n) + 9) \\ &< (1 + \frac{5}{n}) \cdot (\frac{3}{2} \cdot n + 0.05595 \cdot \frac{n}{\log(n)} + \frac{10}{3} \cdot \log(n) + 9) < \frac{3}{2} \cdot n + 0.06 \cdot \frac{n}{\log(n)}. \end{aligned}$$

This proves assertion (i).

Next, we consider assertion (ii). For $x \geq e^{31}$, we have $\log(x) \geq 31$. Then by (eq5) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
f_3(x) &= \pi\left(\frac{2}{3}\sqrt{x \log(x)}\right) - \pi\left(\sqrt{x/\log(2)}\right) \\
&\geq \frac{\frac{2}{3}\sqrt{x \log(x)}}{\log\left(\frac{2}{3}\sqrt{x \log(x)}\right)} - \frac{\sqrt{x/\log(2)}}{\log\left(\sqrt{x/\log(2)}\right)} \left(1 + \frac{1.082}{\log\left(\sqrt{x/\log(2)}\right)}\right) \\
&\geq \frac{\frac{4}{3}\sqrt{x \log(x)}}{\log(x) + \log \log(x)} - \frac{2\sqrt{x/\log(2)}}{\log(x) + \log \log(x)} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\log \log(x)}{\log(x)}\right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1.082 \times 2}{\log(x) - \log \log(2)}\right) \\
&\geq \frac{\frac{4}{3}\sqrt{x \log(x)}}{\log(x) + \log \log(x)} - \frac{\sqrt{x} \cdot 2/\sqrt{\log(2)}}{\log(x) + \log \log(x)} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\log(31)}{31}\right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{1.082 \times 2}{31 - \log \log(2)}\right) \\
&> \frac{\frac{4}{3}\sqrt{x} \cdot (\sqrt{\log(x)} - 2.14)}{\log(x) + \log \log(x)}.
\end{aligned}$$

To estimate $f_4(x)$, we shall write $\alpha = \sqrt{x/\log(2)}$ and $\beta = \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{x \log(x)}$ for convenience. For $x \geq e^{31}$, by (eq5) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
f_4(x) &= \sum_{\alpha < p \leq \beta} p = \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} p \cdot d(\pi(t)) = \beta \cdot \pi(\beta) - \alpha \cdot \pi(\alpha) - \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \pi(t) \cdot dt \\
&< \beta \cdot \pi(\beta) - \alpha \cdot \pi(\alpha) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\alpha}^{\beta} d\left(\frac{t^2}{\log(t)}\right) \\
&= \beta \cdot \pi(\beta) - \frac{\beta^2}{2 \log(\beta)} - \alpha \cdot \pi(\alpha) + \frac{\alpha^2}{2 \log(\alpha)} \\
&< \frac{\beta^2}{2 \log(\beta)} \left(1 + \frac{2.164}{\log(\beta)}\right) < \frac{4}{9}x \cdot \left(1 + \frac{4.33}{\log(x)}\right).
\end{aligned}$$

This proves assertion (ii). □

Proposition 2.9. *Let (a, b, c) be a triple of non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b = c$, $l \geq 11$ be a prime number. Write $N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |abc|/\gcd(16, abc)$. Suppose that (a) $l \neq 13$; or (b) $16 \mid abc$. Then with $f_2(l)$ defined in Lemma 2.8, (i), we have*

$$\begin{aligned}
\log(N) &\leq \left(3 + \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + \sum_{p: p=l \text{ or } l|v_p(N)} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) + 3f_2(l). \\
&\stackrel{\leq}{n \geq 2 \cdot 10^5} \left(3 + \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + \sum_{p: p=l \text{ or } l|v_p(N)} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) + \frac{9}{2} \cdot n + 0.18 \cdot \frac{n}{\log(n)}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Proceeding with the notation of Proposition 2.7, we shall estimate the upper bound of $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l)$ via Remark 1.13.2. Recall that \mathfrak{R}_l consists of the following data:

$$\begin{aligned}
l_0 &= l, \quad e_0 = 3, \quad S_0 = \{2, 3, l\}, \quad S_{\text{gen}}^{\text{multi}} = \{1, 3, l, 3l\}, \quad S_2^{\text{good}} = \{e : e \mid 48, 2 \mid e\}, \\
S_3^{\text{good}} &= \{2, 6, 8\}, \quad S_l^{\text{good}} = \{l - 1, l(l - 1), l^2 - 1\}, \quad S_2^{\text{multi}} = \{2, 6, 2l, 6l\}, \\
S_3^{\text{multi}} &= \{2, 6, 2l, 6l\}, \quad S_l^{\text{multi}} = \{l - 1, 3(l - 1), l(l - 1), 3l(l - 1)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Following the notation of Remark 1.13.2, for $p \neq 2, 3, l$, we have $e_0(p) = 3l$; for $p \in \{2, 3, l\}$, we have $e_0(2) = \max\{48, 6l\} \leq 6l$, $d_0(2) = 5$, $e_0(3) = 6l$, $d_0(3) = 2$, $e_0(l) = 3l(l - 1)$,

$d_0(l) = 2$. Then by (1.21) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{l^2 + l - 12}{l^2 + 5l} \cdot \text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l) &\leq \log(\pi) + \sum_{p \leq e_0(p)+1} \left(\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_0(p)} \right) \cdot \log(p) \\ &+ \sum_{p \in S_0} d_0(p) \cdot \log(p) + \sum_{e_0(p) > p(p-1)} \log\left(\frac{e_0(p)}{p-1}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

We shall estimate the partial sums in the right hand of (2.8).

For $p \in \{2, 3, l\}$, we have $\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_0(p)} < \left(\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{3l}\right) + \frac{p-1}{3l}$. For $p \notin \{2, 3, l\}$, $e_0(p) = 3l$. If we have $p \leq e_0(p) + 1 = 3l + 1$, then since p is a prime number, we have $p \leq 3l - 2$. Hence we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{p \leq e_0(p)+1} \left(\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{e_0(p)} \right) \cdot \log(p) \\ &\leq \sum_{p \leq 3l-2} \left(\frac{1}{p-1} + 1 - \frac{p-1}{3l} \right) \cdot \log(p) + \frac{\log(2) + 2\log(3) + (l-1)\log(l)}{3l}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

Since $S_0 = \{2, 3, l\}$, we have

$$\sum_{p \in S_0} d_0(p) \cdot \log(p) = d_0(2) \cdot \log(2) + d_0(3) \cdot \log(3) + d_0(l) \cdot \log(l) = \log(2^5 \cdot 3^2 \cdot l^2). \quad (2.10)$$

For $p \notin \{2, 3, l\}$, $e_0(p) = 3l$. If we have $p(p-1) < e_0(p) = 3l$, then $p < \sqrt{3l} + 1 < l$. Since $e_0(2) = 6l$, $e_0(3) = 6l$, $e_0(l) = 3l(l-1)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{e_0(p) > p(p-1)} \log\left(\frac{e_0(p)}{p-1}\right) &\leq \log\left(\frac{e_0(2)}{3l}\right) + \log\left(\frac{2e_0(3)}{3l}\right) + \sum_{p < \sqrt{3l}+1} \log\left(\frac{3l}{p-1}\right) + \log\left(\frac{e_0(l)}{l-1}\right) \\ &< \sum_{p < \sqrt{3l}+1} \log\left(\frac{3l}{p-1}\right) + \log(24l). \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

Finally, since $l \geq 11$, by combining (2.8), (2.9), (2.10), (2.11) and Lemma 2.8, (i), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l) &< \frac{l^2 + 5l}{l^2 + l - 12} \cdot (f_1(3l) + \log(\pi) + \frac{\log(2) + 2\log(3) + (l-1)\log(l)}{3l} + \log(2^5 \cdot 3^2 \cdot l^2) \\ &+ \log(20l)) < \frac{l^2 + 5l}{l^2 + l - 12} \cdot (f_1(3l) + \frac{10}{3} \cdot \log(l) + 9) = f_2(l) \underset{n \geq 2 \cdot 10^5}{<} \frac{3}{2} \cdot n + 0.06 \cdot \frac{n}{\log(n)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

3 Effective abc inequalities

In this section, we focus on effective versions of abc inequalities over the rational number field.

Lemma 3.1. *Let N be a positive integer, $h \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(N)$. Let S be a finite set of prime numbers ≥ 5 , with cardinality $n \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |S| \geq 2$. Let p_0 be the smallest prime number in S .*

Let $2 \leq k \leq n$ be an integer, $k(S)$ be the the product of the smallest k numbers in S . Suppose that $k(S) > h/\log(2)$.

For each prime number l , write $N_l \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p:l|v_p(N)} p^{v_p(N)}$. For each $l \in S$, suppose that

$$\sum_{p:p \neq l, l|v_p(N)} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) \leq \left(3 + \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + 3 \text{Vol}(l). \quad (3.1)$$

for some real number $\text{Vol}(l) \geq 0$.

(i) Write

$$A \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{p \in S : p \mid N\}, \quad B \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{p \mid N : \exists l \in S, l \mid v_p(N)\}, \quad C \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{p \mid N : p \notin (A \cup B)\};$$

$$N_A \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p \in A} p^{v_p(N)}, \quad N_B \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p \in B} p^{v_p(N)}, \quad N_C \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p \in C} p^{v_p(N)}.$$

Then we have

$$\sum_{p \in S} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) = \log(N_A), \quad \sum_{p \in S} \log(N_p) \leq (k-1) \cdot \log(N_B).$$

(ii) Write

$$a_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}, \quad a_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{3}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \text{Vol}(l), \quad a_3 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{l \in S} \log(l).$$

Then we have

$$h \leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + a_2 + \frac{kh}{n},$$

(iii) With the notation in assertion (ii), we have

$$h \leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N_C) + \left(\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3 + a_1}{p_0}\right)(h - \log(N_C)) + a_2 + (3 + a_1)a_3.$$

Proof. First, we consider assertion (i). By the definition of the set A , we have

$$\sum_{p \in S} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) = \sum_{p:p \in S, p|N} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) = \sum_{p \in A} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) = \log(N_A).$$

By the definition of N_p , We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \in S} \log(N_p) &= \sum_{p \in S} \sum_{l:l|N, p|v_l(N)} v_l(N) \cdot \log(l) = \sum_{p \in S} \sum_{l:l \in B, p|v_l(N)} v_l(N) \cdot \log(l) \\ &= \sum_{l \in B} v_l(N) \cdot \log(l) \cdot \left(\sum_{p:p \in S, p|v_l(N)} 1 \right). \end{aligned}$$

Now for each prime number $l \mid N$, we claim that $\sum_{p:p \in S, p|v_l(N)} 1 \leq k-1$, which can be proved by contradiction as follows. Assume that $p_1, \dots, p_k \in S$ are k distinct prime numbers, such that $p_i \mid v_l(N)$ for $1 \leq i \leq k$. Then $\prod_{1 \leq i \leq k} p_i \geq k(S) > h/\log(2)$ and $\prod_{1 \leq i \leq k} p_i \mid v_l(N)$. Hence

$$h = \log(N) \geq v_l(N) \cdot \log(l) \geq \prod_{1 \leq i \leq k} p_i \cdot \log(2) > (h/\log(2)) \cdot \log(2) = h.$$

— a contradiction. Thus the claim is true.

By the claim we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{p \in S} \log(N_p) &= \sum_{l \in B} v_l(N) \cdot \log(l) \cdot \left(\sum_{p: p \in S, p|v_l(N)} 1 \right) \\ &\leq (k-1) \cdot \sum_{l \in B} v_l(N) \cdot \log(l) = (k-1) \cdot \log(N_B). \end{aligned}$$

This proves assertion (i).

Next, we consider assertion (ii). By (3.1), for each $l \in S$, we have

$$h = \log(N) \leq \left(3 + \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}\right) \cdot \log \operatorname{rad}(N) + 3 \operatorname{Vol}(l) + v_l(N) \cdot \log(l) + \log(N_l). \quad (3.2)$$

Hence by taking the average of (3.2) for $l \in S$ and by assertion (i), we have

$$\begin{aligned} h &\leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \log \operatorname{rad}(N) + a_2 + \frac{1}{n} \cdot \log(N_A) + \frac{k-1}{n} \cdot \log(N_B) \\ &\leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \log \operatorname{rad}(N) + a_2 + \frac{kh}{n}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

This proves assertion (ii).

Finally, we consider assertion (iii). By the definition of N_A , N_B , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \log \operatorname{rad}(N_A) &= \sum_{p \in A} \log(p) \leq \sum_{p \in S} \log(p) = a_3, \\ \log(N_B) &= \sum_{p \in B} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) \geq \sum_{p \in B} p_0 \cdot \log(p) = p_0 \cdot \log \operatorname{rad}(N_B). \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \log \operatorname{rad}(N) &\leq \log \operatorname{rad}(N_A) + \log \operatorname{rad}(N_B) + \log \operatorname{rad}(N_C) \\ &\leq \log \operatorname{rad}(N_C) + \frac{1}{p_0} \cdot \log(N_B) + a_3. \end{aligned}$$

Then by (3.3) and $\log(N_A), \log(N_B) \leq \log(N) - \log(N_C)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} h &\leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \log \operatorname{rad}(N) + a_2 + \frac{1}{n} \cdot \log(N_A) + \frac{k-1}{n} \cdot \log(N_B) \\ &\leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \log \operatorname{rad}(N_C) + (3 + a_1)a_3 + \left(\frac{k-1}{n} + \frac{3+a_1}{p_0}\right) \log(N_B) + \frac{1}{n} \log(N_A) + a_2 \\ &\leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \log \operatorname{rad}(N_C) + \left(\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3+a_1}{p_0}\right) (\log(N) - \log(N_C)) + a_2 + (3 + a_1)a_3. \end{aligned}$$

This proves assertion (iii). □

Theorem 3.2. *Let (a, b, c) be a triple of non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b = c$.*

(i) *Suppose that $\log(|abc|) \geq 700$, then we have*

$$\log(|abc|) \leq 3 \log \operatorname{rad}(abc) + 8 \sqrt{\log(|abc|) \cdot \log \log(|abc|)}.$$

(ii) *Suppose that $\log(|abc|) \geq 3 \cdot 10^{13}$, then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \log(|abc|) &\leq 3 \log \operatorname{rad}(abc) + 3 \sqrt{\log(|abc|) \cdot \log \log(|abc|)} \\ &\quad \cdot \left(1 + \frac{6}{\sqrt{\log \log(|abc|)}} + \frac{15}{\log \log(|abc|)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Write $N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |abc|/\gcd(16, abc)$, $h \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(N)$. We shall proceed with the notation in Lemma 3.1. We will choose suitable S , such that for each $l \in S$, we have $l \geq 11$ and $l \neq 13$. Then by Proposition 2.9 we can take

$$\text{Vol}(l) = f_2(l) \underset{n \geq 2 \cdot 10^5}{\leq} \frac{3}{2} \cdot l + 0.06 \cdot \frac{l}{\log(l)}.$$

For assertion (i), consider the case $h \geq e^{31}$ at first. We shall write

$$k = 2, \quad S = \{l \in P : \sqrt{h/\log(2)} < l \leq \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{h \log(h)}\}.$$

Since $h \geq e^{31}$, for any $l \in S$, we have $l \geq p_0 > \sqrt{h/\log(2)} > e^{15}$. Since $k(S) > p_0^2 > h/\log(2)$ and $n = |S| \geq 2$, the set S satisfies the premise of Lemma 3.1.

Since $\log \text{rad}(N) \leq h$, by Lemma 3.1, (ii) we have

$$h \leq 3 \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + a_1 \cdot h + a_2 + \frac{2h}{n}, \quad (3.4)$$

where

$$a_1 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}, \quad a_2 = \frac{3}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \text{Vol}(l).$$

Since $p_0 > e^{15}$, by Proposition 2.9 we can take

$$\text{Vol}(l) = f_2(l) < \frac{3}{2} \cdot l + 0.06 \cdot \frac{l}{\log(l)} \leq \frac{3}{2} \cdot l + \frac{0.06 \cdot \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{h \log(h)}}{\log(\frac{2}{3}\sqrt{h \log(h)})} \leq \frac{3}{2} \cdot l + \frac{0.08\sqrt{h}}{\sqrt{\log(h)}}$$

for each $l \in S$. Also, by Lemma 2.8, (ii) we have

$$f_3(h) = n = |S| \geq \frac{\frac{4}{3}\sqrt{h} \cdot (\sqrt{\log(h)} - 2.14)}{\log(h) + \log \log(h)}, \quad f_4(h) = \sum_{l \in S} l < \frac{4}{9}h \cdot \left(1 + \frac{4.33}{\log(h)}\right).$$

Hence for $h \geq e^{31}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12} < \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \frac{12}{l} < \frac{12}{p_0} < \frac{12\sqrt{\log(2)}}{\sqrt{h}} < \frac{10}{\sqrt{h}} \\ a_2 &= \frac{3}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \text{Vol}(l) < \frac{9}{2n} \sum_{l \in S} l + 3 \cdot \frac{0.08\sqrt{h}}{\sqrt{\log(h)}} = \frac{9f_4(h)}{2n} + \frac{0.24\sqrt{h}}{\sqrt{\log(h)}}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{9f_4(h)}{2n} + \frac{2h}{n} &< \frac{4h}{n} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{2.165}{\log(h)}\right) = \frac{4h}{f_3(h)} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{2.165}{\log(h)}\right) \\ &< 3\sqrt{h \log(h)} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{2.165}{\log(h)}\right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2.14}{\sqrt{\log(h)}}\right)^{-1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\log \log(h)}{\log(h)}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus we have

$$a_1 \cdot h + a_2 + \frac{2h}{n} < 10\sqrt{h} + \frac{0.24\sqrt{h}}{\sqrt{\log(h)}} + \left(\frac{9f_4(h)}{2n} + \frac{2h}{n}\right) < 3\sqrt{h \log(h)} \cdot g(\log(h)), \quad (3.5)$$

where for $x = \log(h) \geq 31$, we have

$$g(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \left(1 + \frac{2.165}{x}\right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{2.14}{\sqrt{x}}\right)^{-1} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\log(x)}{x}\right) + \frac{10}{3\sqrt{x}} + \frac{0.08}{x} < 1 + \frac{6}{\sqrt{x}} + \frac{14.5}{x}.$$

Then for $h \geq e^{31}$, by (3.4), (3.5) we have

$$\begin{aligned} h - 3 \log \text{rad}(N) &\leq a_1 \cdot h + a_2 + \frac{2h}{n} < 3\sqrt{h \log(h)} \cdot g(\log(h)) \\ &< 3\sqrt{h \log(h)} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{6}{\sqrt{\log(h)}} + \frac{14.5}{\log(h)}\right), \end{aligned}$$

hence for $h \geq e^{31}$, we have

$$h - 3 \log \text{rad}(N) + 4 \log(2) < 3\sqrt{h \log(h)} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{6}{\sqrt{\log(h)}} + \frac{15}{\log(h)}\right) < 8\sqrt{h \log(h)}. \quad (3.6)$$

The computation in [50] shows that for $680 \leq h \leq e^{31}$, we have

$$h - 3 \log \text{rad}(N) + 4 \log(2) < 8\sqrt{h \log(h)}. \quad (3.7)$$

Then (3.7) is true for any $h \geq 680$ by (3.6).

Since $N = |abc|/\text{gcd}(abc, 16)$, we have $h = \log(N) \leq \log(|abc|) \leq h + 4 \log(2)$. Hence when $\log(|abc|) \geq 700$, we have $h \geq \log(|abc|) - 4 \log(2) > 680$. Then by (3.7), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \log(|abc|) - 3 \log \text{rad}(abc) &\leq h - 3 \log \text{rad}(N) + 4 \log(2) < 8\sqrt{h \log(h)} \\ &\leq 8\sqrt{\log(|abc|) \cdot \log \log(|abc|)}. \end{aligned}$$

This proves assertion (i).

For assertion (ii), note that we have $h \geq \log(|abc|) - 4 \log(2) \geq 3 \cdot 10^{13} - 4 \log(2) > e^{31}$. Then assertion (ii) follows easily from (3.6). \square

Corollary 3.3. *Let (a, b, c) be a triple of non-zero coprime integers such that $a + b = c$; ϵ be a positive real number $\leq \frac{1}{10}$. Then we have*

$$|abc| \leq \max\{\exp(400 \cdot \epsilon^{-2} \cdot \log(\epsilon^{-1})), \text{rad}(abc)^{3+3\epsilon}\}. \quad (3.8)$$

Proof. Write

$$h_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 400 \cdot \epsilon^{-2} \cdot \log(\epsilon^{-1}), \quad u_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 64 \cdot (1 + \epsilon^{-1})^2.$$

For real number $x \geq 10$, write

$$f(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(400 \cdot x^2 \cdot \log(x)) - \log \log(400 \cdot x^2 \cdot \log(x)) - \log(64 \cdot (1 + x)^2).$$

For $x \geq 10$, the derivative

$$f'(x) = \frac{2}{x(x+1)} + \frac{\log(400 \log(x)) - 1}{x \log(x) \log(400 \cdot x^2 \cdot \log(x))} > 0.$$

Then since $\epsilon^{-1} \geq 10$, we have

$$f(\epsilon^{-1}) = \log(h_0) - \log \log(h_0) - \log(u_0) \geq f(10) > 0.$$

Hence we have

$$\frac{h_0}{\log(h_0)} > u_0. \quad (3.9)$$

When $|abc| \leq e^{h_0} = \exp(400 \cdot \epsilon^{-2} \cdot \log(\epsilon^{-1}))$, (3.8) is true. Hence we can assume that $|abc| > e^{h_0}$.

Write $h \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(|abc|) > h_0 > 40000$, then by (3.9) we have

$$\frac{h}{\log(h)} > \frac{h_0}{\log(h_0)} > u_0. \quad (3.10)$$

By Theorem 3.2, (i), we have

$$h \leq 3 \log \text{rad}(|abc|) + 8\sqrt{h \cdot \log(h)}.$$

Then by (3.10) and the definition of u_0 , we have

$$\frac{3 \log \text{rad}(|abc|)}{h} \geq 1 - 8\sqrt{\frac{\log(h)}{h}} \geq 1 - \frac{8}{\sqrt{u_0}} = \frac{1}{1 + \epsilon},$$

which implies

$$h = \log(|abc|) \leq (3 + 3\epsilon) \cdot \log \text{rad}(|abc|).$$

Hence

$$|abc| \leq \text{rad}(abc)^{3+3\epsilon}.$$

□

Remark 3.3.1. With the same notation, Corollary 3.3 improves the following inequality in [39], Theorem 5.4:

$$|abc| \leq 2^4 \cdot \max\{\exp(1.7 \cdot 10^{30} \cdot \epsilon^{-166/81}), \text{rad}(abc)^{3+3\epsilon}\}.$$

4 Generalized Fermat Equations

Let $r, s, t \geq 2$ be positive integers. The equation

$$x^r + y^s = z^t, \text{ with } x, y, z \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (\star)$$

is known as the generalized Fermat equation with signature (r, s, t) . A solution (x, y, z) of (\star) is called non-trivial if $xyz \neq 0$, primitive if $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$, and positive if $x, y, z \in \mathbb{N}$.

Finding all the non-trivial primitive solutions to (\star) is a long-standing problem in number theory. The Pythagorean triples, which are the positive solutions to (\star) with signature $(2, 2, 2)$, have been known since ancient times. Fermat's Last Theorem, which is proven by Andrew Wiles in 1994 [49], states that (\star) has no positive primitive solution with signature (n, n, n) , $n \geq 3$. Catalan's conjecture, which is proven by Preda Mihăilescu in 2002 [31], states that if $x = 1$ in (\star) , then the only positive integer solution to $1 + y^s = z^t$ (with $s, t \geq 2$) is $(y, z, s, t) = (2, 3, 3, 2)$.

4.1 A brief survey

The behavior of primitive solutions to (\star) is fundamentally determined by the size of the quantity

$$\chi(r, s, t) = \frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{t} - 1.$$

Here χ is the Euler characteristic of a certain stack associated to (\star) .

For the spherical case where $\chi > 0$, (r, s, t) is a permutation of $(2, 2, t)$, $t \geq 2$, or $(2, 3, t)$, $3 \leq t \leq 5$. In this case, parametrizations for non-trivial primitive solutions for these signatures can be found in Beukers [10], Edwards [26] and Cohen [19], Section 14.

For the Euclidean case where $\chi = 0$, (r, s, t) is a permutation of $(2, 3, 6)$, $(2, 4, 4)$ or $(3, 3, 3)$. In this case, non-trivial primitive solutions for these signatures come from the solution $1^6 + 2^3 = 3^2$, cf. [7], Proposition 6 for a proof.

For the hyperbolic case where $\chi < 0$, the number of primitive solutions for each fixed signature (r, s, t) is finite, cf. Darmon-Granville [22]. The following positive primitive solutions for the hyperbolic case are currently known:

$$\begin{aligned} 1^n + 2^3 = 3^2 \text{ (for } n \geq 7), \quad 2^5 + 7^2 = 3^4, \quad 7^3 + 13^2 = 2^9, \quad 2^7 + 17^3 = 71^2, \\ 3^5 + 11^4 = 122^2, \quad 17^7 + 76271^3 = 21063928^2, \quad 1414^3 + 2213459^2 = 65^7, \\ 9262^3 + 15312283^2 = 113^7, \quad 43^8 + 96222^3 = 30042907^2, \quad 33^8 + 1549034^2 = 15613^3. \end{aligned}$$

Since all known solutions have $\min\{r, s, t\} \leq 2$, Andrew Beal conjectured in 1993 (cf. [29]) that (\star) has no positive primitive solution when $r, s, t \geq 3$. This conjecture is known as the Beal conjecture, also known as the Mauldin conjecture and the Tijdeman-Zagier conjecture.

We shall say a signature (r, s, t) is **solved** if all the non-trivial primitive solutions to the generalized Fermat equation $x^r + y^s = z^t$ are known. Then each signature with $\chi(r, s, t) = \frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{t} - 1 > 0$ is solved.

The generalized Fermat equation (\star) has been solved for many signatures with $\chi \leq 0$, some of them are listed in the following Theorem 4.1.

Theorem 4.1. *For the signatures (r, s, t) listed below, the generalized Fermat equation has been solved, i.e. all the non-trivial primitive solutions to $x^r + y^s = z^t$ are related to the known solutions presented above.*

- $(n, n, n), n \geq 3$, cf. Wiles [49], Taylor-Wiles [48], Mochizuki-Fesenko-Hoshi-Minamide-Porowski [39].
- $(n, n, 2), n \geq 4; (n, n, 3), n \geq 3$, cf. Darmon-Merel [23], Poonen [40].
- $(2, 3, n), n \in \{7, 8, 9, 10, 15\}$, cf. Poonen-Schaefer-Stoll [41], Bruin [13, 15], Brown [12], Siksek-Stoll [46]. Also for $n = 11$, which is conditional on generalized Riemann hypothesis, cf. Freitas-Naskręcki-Stoll [28].
- $(2, 4, n), n \geq 4$, cf. Ellenberg [27], Bennett-Ellenberg-Ng [8]; $(2, n, 4), n \geq 4$, Corollary of Bennett-Skinner [9], Bruin [14].
- $(2, 6, n), n \geq 3$, cf. Bennett-Chen [5]; $(2, n, 6), n \geq 3$, cf. Bennett-Chen-Dahmen-Yazdani [7].
- $(2, 2n, 3), 3 \leq n \leq 10^7$ or $n \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$, cf. Chen [16], Dahmen [20].
- $(2n, 2n, 5), n \geq 2$, cf. Bennett [4]; $(2, 2p, 5)$, prime $p \geq 17$, $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, cf. Chen [17].

- $(2, 2n, k), n \geq 2, k \in \{9, 10, 15\}; (3, 3, 2n), (3, 6, n), (4, 2n, 3), n \geq 2; (2m, 2n, 3), m \geq 2$ and $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}; (3, 3p, 2),$ prime $p \equiv 1 \pmod{8},$ cf. Bennett-Chen-Dahmen-Yazdani [6, 7].
- $(3, 3, n), 3 \leq n \leq 10^9,$ cf. Chen-Siksek [18].
- $(3, 4, 5), (5, 5, 7), (5, 7, 7), (5, 5, 19),$ cf. Siksek-Stoll [45], Dahmen-Siksek [21].
- $(p, p, q),$ primes $p \geq q \geq 5; (p, p, q),$ primes $p \geq 5, q > 3\sqrt{p \log_2(p)},$ cf. Bartolomé-Mihăilescu [2].

Remark 4.1.1. Note that if a signature (r, s, t) is solved, then (s, r, t) is solved; if (r, s, t) is solved and $2 \nmid s,$ then $(s, t, r), (t, s, r)$ are solved; when $\chi(r, s, t) \leq 0,$ if (r, s, t) is solved and r', s', t' are positive multiples of r, s, t respectively, then (r', s', t') is solved. Hence many new solved signatures can be obtained from the solved signatures in Theorem 4.1. For more about generalized Fermat equations, cf. Bennett-Mihăilescu-Siksek [3] and Bennett-Chen-Dahmen-Yazdani [7].

Remark 4.1.2. Most of the results in Theorem 4.1 are quoted from the tables in the first section of [7], including the case of signatures $(2, n, 4), n \geq 4.$ As explained by Michael Bennett, the case of signatures $(2, n, 4), n \geq 4$ can be proved in the following way.

(1) The signature $(2, 4, 4)$ is solved by Fermat; Bruin [14] covers the signature $(2, 5, 4);$ Bennett-Chen [5] covers the signature $(2, 6, 4).$ Hence it suffices to prove for $n = 9$ or n is a prime number $\geq 7.$

(2) Suppose that x, y, z are non-zero coprime integers such that $x^2 + y^n = z^4.$ Then we have $(z^2 + x)(z^2 - x) = y^n,$ where $\gcd(z^2 + x, z^2 - x)$ is 1 or 2.

When $\gcd(z^2 + x, z^2 - x) = 1,$ we can write $z^2 + x = y_1^n, z^2 - x = y_2^n,$ where y_1, y_2, z are non-zero coprime integers. Hence we have $2z^2 = y_1^n + y_2^n,$ which has no solution for $n \geq 6$ by Bennett-Skinner [9], Theorem 1.1.

When $\gcd(z^2 + x, z^2 - x) = 2,$ we can write $z^2 + \epsilon x = 2y_1^n, z^2 - \epsilon x = 2^{n-1}y_2^n,$ where y_1, y_2, z are non-zero coprime integers, x, z are odd and $\epsilon \in \{\pm 1\}.$ Hence we have $z^2 = y_1^n + 2^{n-2}y_2^n.$ By Catalan's conjecture, we can show that $|y_1 y_2| \neq 1.$ Then when $n \geq 7$ is a prime number, the equation $z^2 = y_1^n + 2^{n-2}y_2^n$ has no solution by Bennett-Skinner [9], Theorem 1.2.

(3) We are now left to prove the case where $n = 9$ and y is even. Since $x^2 - z^4 = (-y^3)^3$ and $8 \mid y^3,$ by comparing to the parametrizations in Cohen [19], Section 14.4.1, we can assume that $y^3 = 8st(s^3 - 16t^3)(s^3 + 2t^3),$ where s, t are non-zero coprime integers such that s is odd and $3 \nmid (s - t).$

Note that $s, t, s^3 - 16t^3, s^3 + 2t^3$ are coprime with each other, except for $\gcd(s^3 - 16t^3, s^3 + 2t^3) \in \{1, 3, 9\}.$ But since their product is a cube, we must have $\gcd(s^3 - 16t^3, s^3 + 2t^3) = 1,$ and hence $s, t, s^3 - 16t^3, s^3 + 2t^3$ are cubes.

Write $s^3 + 2t^3 = r^3,$ where r, s, t are non-zero coprime integers. Then one can check that $(\frac{6t}{r-s}, \frac{9(r+s)}{r-s})$ is a rational point on the elliptic curve $E : Y^2 = X^3 - 27.$ E has Mordell-Weil rank 0, and only has the rational points corresponding to the point at infinity and $(X, Y) = (3, 0).$ Hence we have $(\frac{6t}{r-s}, \frac{9(r+s)}{r-s}) = (3, 0)$ or $r - s = 0,$ thus $(r, s, t) = \pm(1, -1, 1), \pm(1, 1, 0).$ But then $y^3 = 8st(s^3 - 16t^3)(s^3 + 2t^3) \in \{0, 17\},$ which is impossible.

4.2 Upper bounds

Let $r, s, t \geq 2$ be positive integers. Throughout this subsection, we shall assume that (x, y, z) is a positive primitive solution to the generalized Fermat equation $x^r + y^s = z^t.$

We shall prove upper bounds for $\log(x^r y^s z^t)$.

Write $a = x^r, b = y^s, c = z^t$, then (a, b, c) is a triple of positive coprime integers such that $a + b = c$. We shall follow the notation of Lemma 3.1 and make some assumptions:

(1) $N \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |abc| / \gcd(16, abc)$, $h \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(N)$. For each prime number l , $N_l \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p:l|v_p(N)} p^{v_p(N)}$.

(2) S is a finite set of prime numbers ≥ 11 , with cardinality $n \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |S| \geq 2$; $2 \leq k \leq n$ is an integer, $k(S)$ is the the product of the smallest k numbers in S ; write $u_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min\{r, s, t\} \geq 2$, write p_0 for the smallest prime number in S . When $u_0 < 4$, suppose that for any $13 \notin S$.

(3) For each $l \in S$, suppose that

$$\sum_{p:p \neq l, l|v_p(N)} v_p(N) \cdot \log(p) \leq \left(3 + \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}\right) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N) + 3 \text{Vol}(l). \quad (4.1)$$

for some real number $\text{Vol}(l) \geq 0$. The value of $\text{Vol}(l)$ can be taken as the value of $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}_l)$ in Proposition 2.9; or $\text{Vol}(\mathfrak{R}'_l)$ in Remark 2.7.1 when $u_0 \geq 4$, since we have $v_2(abc) = v_2(x^r y^s z^t) \geq u_0 \geq 4$.

(4) Write

$$A \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{p \in S : p \mid N\}, \quad B \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{p \mid N : \exists l \in S, l \mid v_p(N)\}, \quad C \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{p \mid N : p \notin (A \cup B)\};$$

$$N_A \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p \in A} p^{v_p(N)}, \quad N_B \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p \in B} p^{v_p(N)}, \quad N_C \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \prod_{p \in C} p^{v_p(N)};$$

$$a_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \frac{11l + 31}{l^2 + l - 12}, \quad a_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{3}{n} \sum_{l \in S} \text{Vol}(l), \quad a_3 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{l \in S} \log(l).$$

Lemma 4.2. *Proceeding with the above notation, write*

$$r' \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min\{r, s\}, \quad s' \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\{r, s\}, \quad 0 \leq h_C \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(N_C) \leq h = \log(N).$$

(i) *We have*

$$\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \frac{1}{u_0} h_C + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}.$$

(ii) *If $t \leq r'$, then*

$$\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \frac{1}{r'} (h_C - h) + \left(\frac{1}{2t} + \frac{1}{2r'}\right) h + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}.$$

(iii) *If $t = r'$, then*

$$\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \frac{1}{s'} (h_C - h) + \left(\frac{1}{t} + \frac{1}{s'}\right) \cdot \frac{2th}{3t - 1} + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}.$$

(iv) *If $t \geq r'$, then*

$$\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \frac{1}{t} (h_C - h) + \max\left\{\frac{1}{2t} + \frac{1}{2r'}, \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{t}\right)\right\} \cdot h + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}.$$

Proof. When (a, b, c) is a permutation of $(1, 8, 9)$, we have $u_0 = r' = 2$ and $\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \log(3) < 2 \log(2) = \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}$, thus the lemma is true. Now assume that (a, b, c) is not a permutation of $(1, 8, 9)$, and assume without loss of generality that $r \leq s$, then $r' = r$, $s' = s$.

Since $a + b = c$ and (a, b, c) is not a permutation of $(1, 8, 9)$, we have $a, b, c, x, y, z \geq 2$ by Catalan's conjecture (now Mihăilescu's theorem, cf. [31]). Hence

$$a, b < c < (abc)^{1/2} \leq (16N)^{1/2}. \quad (4.2)$$

Write $v \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\{v_2(abc), 4\}$, then $abc = 2^v N$. Write $N'_C \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 2^v N_C \leq 16N_C$ if $2 \mid N_C$, and write $N'_C \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} N_C$ if $2 \nmid N_C$. Then for each $p \mid N_C$, we have $v_p(N'_C) = v_p(abc)$. Hence we can assume that $N_C \mid N'_C = x_1^r y_1^s z_1^t \leq 16N_C$ for some $x_1 \mid x, y_1 \mid y, z_1 \mid z$. Then

$$\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \log(x_1 y_1 z_1), \log(N'_C) \leq \log(16N_C) = h_C + 4 \log(2). \quad (4.3)$$

For assertion (i), by (4.3) we have

$$\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \log(x_1 y_1 z_1) \leq \frac{1}{u_0} \log(x_1^r y_1^s z_1^t) = \frac{1}{u_0} \log(N'_C) \leq \frac{1}{u_0} h_C + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}.$$

For assertion (ii), since $t \leq r' = r \leq s$, we have $u_0 = t$. Then by (4.2), (4.3) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{rad}(N_C) &\leq \log(x_1 y_1 z_1) = \frac{1}{r} \log(x_1^r y_1^r z_1^t) + \left(\frac{1}{t} - \frac{1}{r}\right) \log(z_1^t) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r} \log(N'_C) + \left(\frac{1}{t} - \frac{1}{r}\right) \log(c) \leq \frac{1}{r} \log(16N_C) + \left(\frac{1}{2t} - \frac{1}{2r}\right) \log(16N) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r} h_C + \left(\frac{1}{2t} - \frac{1}{2r}\right) \log(N) + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}. \end{aligned}$$

For assertion (iii), since $t = r' = r \leq s$, we have $u_0 = t$. Since $z = c^{1/t} > a^{1/t} = x > 1$, we have $2 \leq x \leq z - 1$, and

$$b = y^s = z^t - x^t \geq z^t - (z - 1)^t > z^{t-1} > (xz)^{(t-1)/2} = (ac)^{(t-1)/(2t)}. \quad (4.4)$$

Then

$$\log(x_1^r z_1^t) = \log(ac) < \frac{2t}{3t-1} \log(abc) \leq \frac{2t}{3t-1} \log(16N).$$

Hence we have

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{rad}(N_C) &\leq \log(x_1 y_1 z_1) = \frac{1}{s} \log(x_1^t y_1^s z_1^t) + \left(\frac{1}{t} - \frac{1}{s}\right) \log(x_1^t z_1^t) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{s} \log(16N_C) + \left(\frac{1}{t} - \frac{1}{s}\right) \cdot \frac{2t}{3t-1} \log(16N) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{s} h_C + \left(\frac{1}{t} - \frac{1}{s}\right) \cdot \frac{2th}{3t-1} + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}. \end{aligned}$$

For assertion (iv), let $\ell_a = \log(a)/\log(abc)$, $\ell_b = \log(b)/\log(abc)$, $\ell_c = \log(c)/\log(abc)$. Then $0 \leq \ell_a, \ell_b \leq \ell_c$ and $\ell_a + \ell_b + \ell_c = 1$. Hence $\ell_a, \ell_b \leq \ell_c \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and $\ell_a + \ell_b \leq \frac{2}{3}$. Consider about the upper bound of $\left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t}\right)\ell_a + \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t}\right)\ell_b$.

If $\ell_a \leq \ell_b$, then since $\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t} > \frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t}$, we have $\left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t}\right)\ell_a + \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t}\right)\ell_b \leq \left(\left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t}\right)\right) \cdot \frac{\ell_a + \ell_b}{2} \leq \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} - \frac{2}{t}\right)$.

Case 2: $\ell_a \geq \ell_b$. Then we have $\ell_b \leq 1 - 2\ell_a$ and $\frac{1}{3} \leq \ell_a \leq \frac{1}{2}$. Hence $(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_a + (\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_b \leq (\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_a + (\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t})(1 - 2\ell_a) = \frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} - \frac{2}{t}) + (\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{t} - \frac{2}{s})(\ell_a - \frac{1}{3})$. If $\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{t} \leq \frac{2}{s}$, by taking $\ell_a = \frac{1}{3}$, we can get $(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_a + (\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_b \leq \frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} - \frac{2}{t})$; if $\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{t} \geq \frac{2}{s}$, by taking $\ell_a = \frac{1}{2}$, we can get $(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_a + (\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_b \leq \frac{1}{2r} - \frac{1}{2t}$.

In conclusion, we have

$$(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_a + (\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_b \leq \max\{\frac{1}{2r} - \frac{1}{2t}, \frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} - \frac{2}{t})\}.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \log \text{rad}(N_C) &\leq \log(x_1 y_1 z_1) = \frac{1}{t} \log(x_1^t y_1^s z_1^t) + (\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t}) \log(x_1^r) + (\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t}) \log(y_1^s) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{t} \log(16N_C) + ((\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_a + (\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{t})\ell_b) \log(abc) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{t} (h_C - h) + \max\{\frac{1}{2r} + \frac{1}{2t}, \frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{t})\} + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 4.2.1. Write $\bar{u} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{1}{3}(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{t})$. When $\frac{2}{s'} \leq \frac{1}{r'} + \frac{1}{t}$, we have $\bar{u} \leq \frac{1}{2r'} + \frac{1}{2t}$, hence by Lemma 4.2, (ii) and (iv), we have

$$\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \frac{h_C - h}{\max\{r', t\}} + (\frac{1}{2t} + \frac{1}{2r'})h + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}.$$

When $\frac{2}{s'} \geq \frac{1}{r'} + \frac{1}{t}$, we have $r' \leq t$, and $\frac{1}{2r'} + \frac{1}{2t} \leq \bar{u} \leq \frac{2}{3r'} + \frac{1}{3t}$, hence by Lemma 4.2, (ii) and (iv), we have

$$\log \text{rad}(N_C) \leq \frac{h_C - h}{t} + (\frac{2}{3r'} + \frac{1}{3t})h + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0}.$$

Lemma 4.3. *Proceeding with the above notation, and suppose that $k(S) > h/\log(2)$. Recall that $r' = \min\{r, s\}$, $s' = \max\{r, s\}$, $u_0 = \min\{r, s, t\}$. We shall define b_1 in any of the following cases:*

- (a) When $\frac{2}{s'} \leq \frac{1}{r'} + \frac{1}{t}$, write $b_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\{\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3+a_1}{p_0}, \frac{1}{2}(\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3+a_1}{p_0}) + \frac{3+a_1}{2u_0}, (3+a_1) \cdot (\frac{1}{2r'} + \frac{1}{2t})\}$.
- (b) When $\frac{2}{s'} \geq \frac{1}{r'} + \frac{1}{t}$, write $b_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\{\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3+a_1}{p_0}, \frac{1}{3}(\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3+a_1}{p_0}) + \frac{2(3+a_1)}{3r'}, (3+a_1) \cdot (\frac{2}{3r'} + \frac{1}{3t})\}$.
- (c) When $t = r'$, write $b_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max\{\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3+a_1}{p_0}, (\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3+a_1}{p_0}) \cdot \frac{t-1}{3t-1} + \frac{2(3+a_1)}{3t-1}, (3+a_1) \cdot \frac{2s'+(t-1)}{s'(3t-1)}\}$.

We shall write $b_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} a_2 + (3+a_1) \cdot (a_3 + \frac{4 \log(2)}{u_0})$. Then we have

$$h \leq b_1 \cdot h + b_2. \tag{4.5}$$

Hence if $b_1 < 1$ and $k(S) \cdot \log(2) > \frac{b_2}{1-b_1}$, then $h = \log(N)$ cannot belong to the interval

$$(\frac{b_2}{1-b_1}, k(S) \cdot \log(2)).$$

Proof. Since $k(S) > h/\log(2)$, we can make use of Lemma 3.1. We shall only prove the case when b_1 is defined in case (a), Other cases can be proved similarly.

Recall that we have

$$0 \leq h_C \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(N_C) \leq h = \log(N).$$

By Lemma 3.1 (iii), we have

$$h \leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \log \text{rad}(N_C) + \left(\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3 + a_1}{p_0}\right)(h - h_C) + a_2 + (3 + a_1)a_3. \quad (4.6)$$

When $0 \leq h_C \leq \frac{1}{2}h$, by (4.6) and Lemma 4.2 (i), we have

$$h \leq (3 + a_1) \cdot \frac{h_C}{u_0} + \left(\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3 + a_1}{p_0}\right)(h - h_C) + b_2. \quad (4.7)$$

The right hand of (4.7) is linear in h_C , reaching its maximal value at $h_C = 0$ or $h_C = \frac{1}{2}h$. Hence by (4.7) we have

$$h \leq \max\left\{\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3 + a_1}{p_0}, \frac{k}{2n} + \frac{3 + a_1}{2p_0} + \frac{3 + a_1}{2u_0}\right\} \cdot h + b_2 \leq b_1 \cdot h + b_2.$$

When $\frac{1}{2}h \leq h_C \leq h$, by (4.6) and Remark 4.2.1, we have

$$h \leq (3 + a_1)\left(\frac{h_C - h}{\max\{r', t\}} + \left(\frac{1}{2t} + \frac{1}{2r'}\right)h\right) + \left(\frac{k}{n} + \frac{3 + a_1}{p_0}\right)(h - h_C) + b_2. \quad (4.8)$$

The right hand of (4.8) is linear in h_C , reaching its maximal value at $h_C = \frac{1}{2}h$ or $h_C = h$. Hence by (4.8) we have

$$h \leq \max\left\{\frac{k}{2n} + \frac{3 + a_1}{2p_0} + \frac{3 + a_1}{2u_0}, \frac{3 + a_1}{2t} + \frac{3 + a_1}{2r'}\right\} \cdot h + b_2 \leq b_1 \cdot h + b_2.$$

Hence when b_1 is defined in case (a), we must have (4.5), and then the lemma follows. \square

Theorem 4.4. *Let $r, s, t \geq 3$ be positive integers. Write*

$$S(r, s, t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}^3 : x^r + y^s = z^t, \gcd(x, y, z) = 1\}$$

for the finite set of positive primitive solutions to the generalized Fermat equation with signature (r, s, t) . Define

$$f(r, s, t) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sup_{(x, y, z) \in S} \log(x^r y^s z^t) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0},$$

where we shall write $f(r, s, t) = 0$ if $S(r, s, t)$ is an empty set.

Then the explicit upper bounds for $f(r, s, t)$ are presented in Table 1. In particular, we have $f(r, s, t) \leq 573$ for $r, s, t \geq 8$; $f(r, s, t) \leq 907$ for $r, s, t \geq 5$; $f(r, s, t) \leq 2283$ for $r, s, t \geq 4$; $f(r, s, t) \leq 14750$ for $\min\{r, s\} \geq 4$ or $t \geq 4$; and $f(r, s, t) \leq 24626$ for $r, s, t \geq 3$.

Proof. Suppose that $S(r, s, t) \neq \emptyset$, and let $(x, y, z) \in S(r, s, t)$ be a positive primitive solution to $x^r + y^s = z^t$. Write $(a, b, c) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (x^r, y^s, z^t)$, $h \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \log(x^r y^s z^t) = \log(abc)$, then $a + b = c$ and $\gcd(a, b, c) = 1$.

Table 1: Upper bounds for $f(r, s, t)$

$(\min\{r, s\}, t)$	Bounds	$\min\{r, s, t\}$	Bounds
(3, 3)	24626	4	2283
(3, 4)	14750	5	907
(3, n), $n \geq 5$	6648	6	697
(4, 3)	7254	7	635
(n , 3), $n \geq 5$	3406	≥ 8	573

We shall prove that

$$\log \operatorname{rad}(abc) \leq \log(xyz) < \frac{5}{16} \cdot h, \quad \text{for } h \geq \log(4). \quad (4.9)$$

Assume without loss of generality that $s \geq r$. Then since $(r, s, t) \neq (3, 3, 3)$, which is proved by Euler, we have $t \geq 4$; or $s \geq r \geq 4$; or $s \geq 4$, $r = t = 3$.

When $t \geq 4$, since $c > a, b$, we have $abc > a^{\frac{12}{11}} b^{\frac{12}{11}} c^{\frac{9}{11}} = x^{\frac{12r}{11}} y^{\frac{12s}{11}} z^{\frac{9t}{11}} \geq (xyz)^{\frac{36}{11}}$. Hence $\log \operatorname{rad}(abc) \leq \log(xyz) < \frac{11}{36} \log(abc) = \frac{11}{36} h < \frac{5}{16} h$.

When $s \geq r \geq 4$, since $2ab \geq c$ by $a + b = c$, we have $2^{\frac{1}{2}} abc > a^{\frac{6}{7}} b^{\frac{6}{7}} c^{\frac{8}{7}} = x^{\frac{6r}{7}} y^{\frac{6s}{7}} z^{\frac{8t}{7}} \geq (xyz)^{\frac{24}{7}}$. Hence when $h \geq \log(4)$, we have $\log \operatorname{rad}(abc) \leq \log(xyz) < \frac{7}{24} \log(abc) + \frac{\log(2)}{24} = \frac{7}{24} h + \frac{\log(2)}{24} \leq \frac{5}{16} h$.

When $s \geq 4$, $r = t = 3$, write $\lambda = \frac{s-3}{s+1} \geq \frac{1}{5}$ by $s \geq 4$. Since $b = y^s > z^2 > xz$ by (4.4), we have $abc = x^3 y^s z^3 > x^{3+\lambda} y^{s-s\lambda} z^{3+\lambda} = (xyz)^{3+\lambda} \geq (xyz)^{\frac{16}{5}}$. Hence $\log \operatorname{rad}(abc) \leq \log(xyz) < \frac{5}{16} \log(abc) = \frac{5}{16} h$. This proves (4.9).

Assume that $h \geq \log(4)$, then by Theorem 3.2, (i) and (4.9), we have

$$h \leq 3 \log \operatorname{rad}(abc) + 9\sqrt{h \cdot \log(h)} \leq \frac{15}{16} \cdot h + 9\sqrt{h \cdot \log(h)},$$

which is impossible for $h \geq 10^6$. Hence we must have $h < 10^6$. The computation in [50] based on Lemma 4.3 shows that if $h < 10^6$, then h must be less than the upper bounds presented in Table 1. Hence the theorem is proven. \square

By making use of the ‘‘entirely elementary estimate’’ for positive solutions of the Fermat equation presented in [39], Lemma 5.7, we shall provide an alternative approach to prove the ‘‘Fermat’s Last Theorem’’ for prime exponents ≥ 11 .

Corollary 4.5. *Let*

$$p \geq 11$$

be a prime number. Then there does not exist any triple (x, y, z) of positive integers that satisfies the Fermat equation

$$x^p + y^p = z^p.$$

Proof. By dividing (x, y, z) by their greatest common divisor, we shall assume that (x, y, z) is a triple of positive coprime integers such that $x^p + y^p = z^p$ and $x < y < z$.

Since

$$x^p = z^p - y^p \geq z^p - (z-1)^p > z^{p-1},$$

we have

$$x^p y^p z^p > z^{p-1} \cdot (z^p - z^{p-1}) \cdot z^p > (z-1)^{3p-1}. \quad (4.10)$$

Since $p \geq 11$, by Theorem 4.1, we have $\log(x^p y^p z^p) \leq 600$. Then by (4.10), we have

$$\log(z - 1) < \frac{1}{3p - 1} \cdot \log(x^p y^p z^p) \leq \frac{600}{3p - 1} < 20. \quad (4.11)$$

However, by the estimate in [39], Lemma 5.7, we have $z > \frac{(p+1)^p}{2}$. Hence for $p \geq 11$, we have

$$\log(z - 1) \geq \log\left(\frac{(p+1)^p}{2}\right) = p \cdot \log(p+1) - \log(2) > 26. \quad (4.12)$$

— a contradiction between (4.11) and (4.12). \square

Remark 4.5.1. (i) To prove Fermat's Last Theorem (FLT), we only need to prove that there does not exist any triple (x, y, z) of positive integers that satisfies the Fermat equation

$$x^n + y^n = z^n,$$

where $n = 4$ or $n = p$ is a prime number ≥ 3 .

(ii) The case $n = 4$ is proved by Fermat using the technique of infinite descent; the case $n = 3$ is proved by Euler; the case $n = 5$ is proved by Dirichlet and Legendre around 1825; the case $n = 7$ is proved by Gabriel Lamé in 1839. All of these cases have elementary proofs.

(iii) in Corollary 4.5, by applying Theorem 4.1 and the elementary estimate found in [39], Lemma 5.7, we have proven FLT for prime exponents ≥ 11 . Hence we conclude that the results of the present paper, combined with the historical proofs for the cases $n = 3, 4, 5, 7$ mentioned in (ii), yield an unconditional new alternative proof [i.e., to the proof of [49]] of Fermat's Last Theorem.

Corollary 4.6. *Let r, s, t be positive integers such that $r, s, t \geq 20$, or (r, s, t) is a permutation of $(3, 3, n)$ for $n \geq 3$. Then there does not exist any triple (x, y, z) of non-zero coprime integers that satisfies the generalized Fermat equation*

$$x^r + y^s = z^t.$$

Proof. Suppose that (x, y, z) is a non-trivial primitive solution to the generalized Fermat equation $x^r + y^s = z^t$. Then by permuting (r, s, t) , we can assume that $x, y, z \geq 1$. Then since $r, s, t \geq 3$, we have $x, y, z \geq 2$ by Catalan's conjecture.

(1) When (r, s, t) is a permutation of $(3, 3, n)$, $n \geq 3$, we have $n > 10^9$ by [18], also cf. Theorem 4.1. However, by Theorem 4.4 we have $\log(2^n) < \log(x^r y^s z^t) \leq 24626$, hence $n < 24626 / \log(2) < 10^5$ — a contradiction!

(2) When $r, s, t \geq 20$, by Theorem 4.4 we have $\log(x^r y^s z^t) < 600$. However, the computation in [50] shows that for any $r, s, t \geq 20$, there does not exist any triple (x, y, z) of positive coprime integers such that $x^r + y^s = z^t$ and $\log(x^r y^s z^t) < 600$ — a contradiction!

The corollary follows from (1) and (2). \square

Remark 4.6.1. In the subsequent paper, we will introduce new insights to further explore the generalized Fermat equations. We will establish new upper bounds for non-trivial primitive solutions and demonstrate the non-existence of such solution for an expanded set of signatures.

References

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